

Conference Proceedings

Crime Prevention Through Environment Design (CPTED)

Explore amazing research papers on phygital security and CPTED principles in emerging sectors.

YEAR: 2022 CONFERENCE

Conference on Crime Prevention Through Environment Design (CPTED)

Date: 8th January 2022

Published By:

School of Planning and Architecture, Delhi

Department of Architecture

4 Block B, IP Estate, New Delhi 110002

Co Published By:

Information Sharing and Analysis Center

10, Temple Road, Vontikoppal, Mysore

support@isacindia.org

8882-560-560

Year: 2022

Edition: First

Language: English

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7700510

Prof. Dr. P.S.N. Rao
Director
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Preface

School of Planning and Architecture, New Delhi, an Institute of National Importance created under an Act of Parliament is at the forefront of built environment-related education, consultancy, and research. This current conference is the pioneering one as it highlights the important concept of Crime Prevention through Environment Design.

This conference has been jointly organised with Information Sharing and Analysis Center, India which is a Non-Governmental Organisation working closely with the government on issues related to security, both physical and cyber. We are very grateful to our Chief Guest, Shri Neeraj Thakur, IPS, Special Commissioner, Delhi Police for gracing the occasion and addressing the audience on important concepts related to urban security and the role of the built environment.

The proceedings are a compilation of path-breaking work done by researchers across the country working on concepts of CPTED.

(Prof. Dr. P.S.N. Rao)

Rajshekhar Pullabhatla

Director, Information Sharing and Analysis Center, India

Message

Information Sharing and Analysis Center strongly believes in advocating the CPTED principles and advancing research in Phygital security, a term that refers to the security of physical and digital spaces. This term is often used in the context of smart cities, where many physical devices and infrastructure are connected to the internet, creating a complex network of interconnected systems.

The concept of Phygital security is based on the idea that physical and digital spaces are interconnected and interdependent and that ensuring the security of one requires the security of the other. For example, in a smart city, the physical security of a building may depend on the digital security of the building's network and security systems. Similarly, the digital security of a city's infrastructure may depend on the physical security of the devices and equipment used to access and manage that infrastructure.

We are grateful to the School of Planning and Architecture, New Delhi, for stepping forward and collaborating with ISAC on this crucial subject. We hope to implement the outcomes of CPTED research with new-age architects in emerging sectors and build a safer and more resilient infrastructure in the nation.

(Rajshekhar Pullabhatla)

Conference Winners

- The paper titled ‘People’s perception of safety on street and its relation to the immediate built Environment: A construct based in Indian communities and street design in the light of CPTED strategies’ – authored by Dr. Parama Mitra and Prof. (Dr) Suchandra Bardhan has been selected for the **Best Paper Award**
- The **paper with Special Mention** was awarded to the paper titled ‘Crime Control through Landscape Development of Neighbourhood Open Spaces’-authored by Prof. Sushama Parashar and Ms.Isha Rane.
- The **Phygital Innovation Award** was awarded to the paper titled ‘Applied Situational Intelligence by Dynamics of Human Context’-authored by Mr. Ravi Reddy and Prof. Ramesh Srikonda.

Editors

- Editor in Chief: Prof. Dr. PSN Rao, Director, School of Planning and Architecture, New Delhi
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- Conference Editor: Dr. Amanish Lohan, Information Sharing and Analysis Center, India

Special Mention

- Dr. Jyoti Pandey Sharma, Professor, was responsible for the oversight over the integrity of the academic and peer review processes in the conference.
- R Biswas for his help in helping the conference. He helped in the plag check process.
- Prof. Dr. Binod Kumar Singh
- Dr. Shuvojit Sarkar, SPA Delhi

Special thanks to our judges:

- Prof. Manoj Mathur
- Lt Col Anuj Srivastava

List of Peer Reviewers:

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Safer Spaces through Accessible Design: Exploring Landscape Architecture and Regional Imagery to Generate Inclusivity and Stewardship - Arunima Chakravarty

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Abstract

The conscious arrangement of design elements in a space can make it a 'place', affording an identity and building a stewardship for its cause. Whether the 'place' is successful or not is often evaluated by the pattern of its usage by its end users. Successfully designed spaces are, in general, safe places. The idea of affording security to a space by dint of design has been explored to a fair extent in the urban realm. In Indian urban areas, there is a lack of healthy public spaces due to lack of proper facilities and/or fewer opportunities of social interaction. The broad categories of crimes that occur in urban areas are theft or burglary, violent crime or assault/harassment and human trafficking. The principles of CPTED can be directed into design approaches for public urban spaces which do not overtly prevent 'criminals' from accessing spaces, but allow them access only to the physical place and not the mind-frame or space-frame of 'committing a crime'. The idea is to protect potential 'victims' by the presence of similar public, encouraging their numbers to a point where the 'victims' themselves are in majority and afford each other security by their mere presence. Urban spaces can be made people friendly by providing aptly designed elements like accessible mobility, weather protection, components that allow for pause like seating or aesthetic features or kiosks, visual and physical access to natural elements like plants, water, soil and even fauna.

The translation of these elements into design can be based on the concept of local or regional imagery and approached through cultural lenses which, in turn can afford a sense of familiarity and ownership in the users. This research paper aims at exploring successful public projects and prospective approaches pertaining to, yet not exclusive to, the field of landscape architecture using principles of CPTED which can help in creating socially safe and inclusive public spaces at the neighbourhood or city scale.

Keywords: stewardship, inclusivity, public, landscape architecture, regional imagery

Highlights/Relevance of Paper

In an increasing globalised and accessible world due to advancing technology, the concept of crime prevention can be optimised by allowing spaces to be accessible, yet closely monitored. This research paper explores the use of contextual design and ecological approaches to deal with design issues, which is the need of the hour.

Urbanisation Trends and Need for Safe Public Spaces

The present-day world is undergoing urbanisation at an unprecedented rate. In the next twenty years, the percentage of population living in urban areas will increase to 60.4%, an increase from 56.2% at the end of the year 2020 (UN-Habitat, 2020). This implies that a large percentage of population shall be exposed to the spaces found in an urban context. The social value of such spaces (and other urban opportunities) will increase if it is equally accessible to all the economic groups of the population. In an insightful work in 1993, eminent geographer Edward Relph subtly compared urbanisation with an environment machine: a mega-machine which comprises of the interacting components of ideologies, economic linkages, institutions and corporations, involving various planning and design approaches. Although this ‘machine’, provides a guaranteed upscaling of economic conditions, yet it somehow diminishes the importance of the human scale. ‘Places, landscapes, buildings, and cities seem largely incidental to its purpose’: urbanisation incidentally leads to the loss of the sense of place and identity, in turn creating a detachment for individuals who do not identify with their place of being (Relph, 2002). This sense of ‘placelessness’ can often lead to detachment from social values and result in creating opportunities for antisocial behaviour. While the psychological courses of the human mind bent towards antisocial behaviour is beyond the realm of this study, the setting in which the individual functions can be examined for creating a place which enhances a sense of belonging and ownership.

Many studies have shown that the quality of a space impacts the behaviour of the person using it. Hence, places which encourage stewardship discourage antisocial behaviour. In his extensive documentation of successful public urban spaces, William H Whyte records the case of the NY Telephone building and the Avenue of America’s Plaza in New York, which was frequented by undesirable persons. The authorities introduced chairs, tables, food facilities and the scenario completely changed. The general public started utilising these facilities, and the undesirable space transformed into a very successful urban space. Seagram’s Plaza, Paley Park

are other examples of public spaces which are frequented by various classes of people yet have had minimal vandalism.

The conscious arrangement of design elements in a space can make it a 'place', affording an identity and building a stewardship for its cause. Whether the 'place' is successful or not is often evaluated by the pattern of its usage by its end users. Successfully designed spaces are, in general, safe places.

Public Spaces in Indian Cities: The Local Context

India, China and Nigeria—are expected to account for up to 35 per cent of the total increase in global urban population from 2018 to 2050 (UN-Habitat, 2020). As new urban areas get planned, it important to focus on designing crime free public spaces. One of the major problems in India is its sheer size of population and the diverse economic strata, due to which it is difficult to create conventional spaces which cater to the diverse needs. However, some public parks and plazas in retail like shopping malls, office etc are still organized. Many traditional Indian Bazaars like the food markets of Sarafa in Indore, Manek Chowk in Ahmedabad are examples of informal public spaces that are deemed considerably safe and active even at late night hours. In the recent years, the transformation of roads in cities like Pune (DP Road, Aundh), Bangalore (TenderSURE roads), Chennai (Sringeri Mutt Road), Coimbatore (Pothy's Junction) etc have proven that inclusive design can result in activated urban spaces. Aimed at increasing road safety, these spaces have also created a safer environment for all commuters and reduced antisocial activities like theft, sexual harassment, public urination etc as well.

There is a need to develop spaces which are more public in nature such that people are acquainted to the idea of community ownership of a place and their roles and responsibilities in upholding the safekeeping of such places. Hence, for a starting idea we need well designed spaces where the population masses can come in and by their own presence and responsibility make these spaces successful and safe.

Creating Public Spaces Encouraging Stewardship

The approach for creating opportunities for public ownership of urban spaces, is to create a sense of place such that it generates a certain identity and recall value in the mind of the user. The presence of people and their subconscious awareness and vigilance should be a handy tool in preventing anti-social elements. Drawing from one of the most popular approaches to safe

design, the principle of ‘eyes on the street’ (Jacobs, 1961), can be approached through a cultural lens. The street can be designed in such a way that it generates a sense of place and people ‘own the street’, consequently becoming agile and responsible consumers of the space.

In many Indian cities, very often the economically weaker section of the society is rendered less priority due to the rapid rate of urbanisation. This stratum of the society hence has to reside in informal, poorly maintained settlements often being victims to demolition, dislocation, relocations etc (Satija, 2016). The Theory of Broken Windows (Wilson & Kelling, 1982) states that if a window in a building is broken and is left unrepaired, all the rest of the windows will soon be broken. This analogy is related to crime in a society: disregard and disrepair in a neighbourhood encourages antisocial activities. The lack of inclusive urban planning and service provisions in any urban space leads to the creation of fear in the minds of the public, and parallelly creates opportunities of crime for the criminals.

In the mid-sixties and seventies, some policies were introduced in New York to encourage the creation of public spaces. The authorities passed a zoning resolution that gave developers a floor area bonus for providing plaza space. For each square foot of plaza space, the builder was allowed 10 feet of additional commercial floor area. This plaza was to be accessible to the public at all times, and the responsibility of maintenance rested with the owners. In 1975, guidelines for the development of public spaces in NY was prepared. It highlighted detail design approaches like seating space, vegetation, retail frontage, lighting, circulation, universal accessibility, food facilities etc (Whyte, 1980). Over time, public spaces developed which were accessible and frequently visited by citizens. A general affinity and awareness for the benefits of such spaces developed, as these provided opportunities for social interaction on multiple scales, and were well maintained.

These kind of Floor Space Index (FSI) incentives need to be explored in the Indian context so that well designed and safe public areas are available to the public so that they can understand the need of such spaces, as well opportunities provided by them. There needs to be a revolutionary mindset change across economic groups whence people start owning public spaces and being responsible for their cause.

An interesting theory which was put forward by Malcom Gladwell explains a ‘tipping point’ as the biography of an idea which explores the epidemic like changes that take place in a

society. Accordingly, these revolutionary changes can be effective by concentrating efforts or resources on key areas (Gladwell, 2000). These key areas then act as stimuli and responses in people and environment interacting with them. Drawing from this analogy, our society needs safe urban public spaces, well designed and maintained, located in strategic areas which invites optimum usage. And the location of this spaces can be carved out in prominent commercial/office/administrative properties by providing FSI incentives as was done by authorities in New York.

Designing Safe Public Spaces

Major part of the paper should be analysis and results section The principles of CPTED are holistic concepts that can be used not only for a crime free design, but also an aesthetic and pleasurable design.

These multi-layered concepts of CPTED, when explored through a cultural lens and implemented through landscaping techniques, can result in comfortable environments for the users. At this point, another interesting point to consider is the very definition of landscape architecture. The word originates from the German word 'landschaft' which literally translates to sculpting the land. In general, the discipline has a misconception as being an art of dealing with only gardens and parks. However, in the present times the need for 'collective landscapes has emerged as a social necessity' (Jellicoe & Jellicoe, 1987) and henceforth it is essential that the larger idea of the discipline is understood. With the negative impacts of urbanization like global warming constricting the popularity of the progress of urbanization, it is essential that any future human centric development should aim at achieving a sense of balance between man and nature. 'Nature' is not limited to the larger masses of it existing in the countryside. Even small pockets of nature in an urban setting needs equal attention and preservation efforts. And man, by his behavioural characteristic and evolution into a higher species is capable of creating a space that is a projection into the natural environment, and yet an abstraction of artistic concepts and abstract ideas.

Studies state there are four primitive behavioural inclinations for an individual (of a species): ingestive, shelter seeking, sexual and exploratory (Appleton, 1975). Individuals tend to 'perform' in environments which provide opportunities to satisfy such needs. Through evolution, human individuals no longer have to fight for survival. Hence, though ingestive and sexual instincts are innate, they have become less pronounced and are subject to a man's desire

rather than a continuous survival response to the ‘physical’ environment. On the other hand, the shelter seeking and exploratory instincts still function subtly in his day-to-day interactions with the physical environment. In landscape architecture theory discourse, the Prospect Refuge Theory is studied which is a development from the behavioural studies explained above. The theory states that an environment or space that affords an individual the ability to see without being seen, is an environment which is aesthetically pleasing and desirable to the individual. Relating this thought back to the sense of place, an environment which is pleasurable has a positive impact on the user and generates in him a certain affinity for the space. Setting this understanding as a basis for the essence of design required, various reference points in our regional and cultural history of settlement pertaining to, yet not exclusive to landscape architecture will be explored. The design approaches will focus on how taking inspirations of instances from our cultural and regional history can help in creating spaces which relate to the users experiencing the space.

Natural Surveillance

This principle addresses design approaches that allow for surveillance as a consequence of the arrangement of elements in the space itself. In a local perspective, the variety of climatic and geographical conditions in India has resulted in many ‘vernacular’ approaches to architecture and planning. Regional imagery is also a consequence of spatial organisation conducive to the local design principles which creates a sense of familiarity and recognition in the minds of the user. The concept of the village chowk or the market square as the public space, the concept of patiyas of Bhopal and otlas of residences along streets that allowed for congregation within the surveillance of the local residents can be inspirations towards placing of public spaces. Another interesting aspect of Indian traditional public spaces is the utilitarian nature of it. The village chabutaras which functioned as the meeting place, the baoris of Gujarat like Adalaj stepwell or Rani-ni-vav at Patan, which functioned as water collection points and resting points for travellers, the ghats along holy rivers which had a ritualistic essence to it are all examples of Indian public spaces which was accessible to the community. The spatial arrangement of these kind of spaces are contextual and relate to our mental image, making a local user comfortable in that space. Hence, modern day approaches like tactical urbanism should include local imagery and spatial techniques rather than finding makeshift solutions to the problem of lack of public spaces in the country.

Natural Access Control

Hierarchy of spaces should be clearly defined in a public realm. Controlled access can be pre-empted through the use of terrain, the use of different species of plants, use of materials to define utility/ flexibility of spaces. A subtle correlation can be made to the fort planning strategies of India where, on a larger scale, much attention was given to the approach into the walled 'space'. A physical barrier like a moat as well as the ramparts themselves were designed alongside the terrain, integrating interestingly designed spaces and defensive measures. The fort of Chittorgarh is an excellent example where the user within the fort experiences an exceptional array of spatial experiences, while from a security point of view, it was one of the most formidable forts in Indian history. This duality of design approach which satisfies both the prevention of assault as well as creates an experience for the user is what should be aimed for.

Territorial Reinforcement

This is the most important principle which can be implemented by the physical manifestation of regional imagery concepts. The use of local materials, local vegetation species, typology of space usage familiar to the local context is essential in making the user feel comfortable in that space. The urban spaces of lower income areas of the city should be especially designed integrating local materials, such that it encourages usage lest they fall into disrepair. The peri urban areas and lower income neighbourhoods generally have many immigrant households from within a short radius around the urban centre. Creating a recall value of the rural countryside using the similar nature of stone, planting and terrain can instil positivity and ownership in the citizens.

Space Management

In the section on the need to create public spaces in key urban areas to generate awareness, the urban plaza guidelines of NY city were highlighted. In the case of these proposed public spaces which are actually a part of commercial or retail establishments, the owners can themselves maintain the spaces from the monetary incomes they get from kiosk revenues or CSR funds etc. However, in other public spaces, there needs to be community groups and initiatives to care for the local public spaces. The Gandhian philosophy of Sarvodaya, upliftment of all or the Panchayati raj system which encouraged self-sufficient villages are valuable inspirations

ingrained in our history. Similarly, self-efficient public spaces need an outlook of inclusivity as well as an organised body who are accountable for its maintenance.

Conclusion and Way Forward

Drawing from inspirations from our local context and history, the Indian approach to the CPTED can be enriched. The challenge is to prevent crime without creating additional physical elements in the space, and by dint of an activated space, encourage healthier interactions in the society. As stated in the Theory of broken windows, any visible signs of crime, disorder and antisocial behaviour may encourage more crime (Wilson & Kelling, 1982). In the same way, any visible signs of regional imagery and familiar cultural elements, can encourage more attachment and community guardianship.

The principles of CPTED can be directed into design approaches which do not overtly prevent ‘criminals’ from accessing spaces, but allow them access only to the physical place and not the mind-frame or space-frame of ‘committing a crime’.

The idea is to protect potential ‘victims’ by the presence of similar public, encouraging their numbers to a point where the ‘victims’ themselves are in majority and afford each other security by their mere presence. Even in an era of high-end technological possibilities relating to surveillance and big data processing, accessing an individual’s mindset is possible only to a certain extent.

The positives of technological advancement are like double edged swords because both the protectors and the prospective wrongdoers have access to a similar domain of data and information. Hence, in such times attaining a sensitivity towards humane emotions, relations and sensibilities should be accorded higher significance in dealing with any social interventions in the urban realm.

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Importance of community participation methods for ensuring safety in urban residential areas- A case of Kollam, Krishna.A.L, Karthik Mohan

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Abstract

Crime and fear of crime are serious in a society that can decline the quality of life. The study focuses on the physical and non-physical approaches to crime prevention in urban residential neighborhoods. People in today's world lock themselves in their homes with little interaction with the outside world. The tragic outcome of this situation will be the feeling of powerlessness. The study begins with the hypothesis that crime reduction strategies through community participation have the ability to restore the sense of power and control over crime and defend against any threat in one's neighborhood. The paper explores the research analysis on the present safety condition of the crime-oriented residential neighborhoods in the Kerala context.

The research was conducted through visual audits, safety audits, and community participation. Three urban residential areas within Kollam Corporation in Kerala were selected and analyzed in order to understand how far the environment has contributed to the unsafe nature. Interview with locals provided an insight into how the residents perceived their own safety. Observation through visual audit was conducted in order to understand how the area functions now and how people use it. Cognitive mapping was done with women, the elderly, and children to ascertain the perception of safety in their neighborhoods. The environmental crime prevention strategies reduce the chances of situational crimes, will improve the quality of spaces, and give an image to the place. One cannot completely reduce crime by doing spatial planning alone and social conditions also need to be considered. Community-based crime prevention brings together many local stakeholders to focus their energies on developing designs to increase community safety while building a sense of connection and belonging among residents.

The major finding of the research through cognitive mapping, visual audits, and impersonal interviews was that crime prevention strategies through community participation have the ability to restore the sense of power and control over crime and defend against any threat in one's neighbourhood.

Keywords: Community participation, safety audits, cognitive mapping, poster presentation, visual audits.

Introduction

According to humanistic psychologist Abraham Maslow, in his article titled “*A Theory of Human Motivation*” introduces his “Hierarchy of Needs” where the second most important basic need for any human being is safety (S. McLeod 2018). A neighborhood should be designed to improve citizens’ health and well-being and increase overall neighborhood safety and social interaction. Fear of crime is an emotional reaction described by a sense of danger and anxiety. Crime and the fear of crime affect societies and contribute to a decline in the quality of life (Bishop 2018). Crime prevention by design strategies along with community planning can reduce the situational crimes that occur in residential neighborhoods. During the 1960s-1970s, it was found that physical changes alone will not reduce crime. Social factors with individuals’ involvement play a role in crime prevention. Hence there is a need to raise the consciousness of planners, policymakers, architects, and households to convince the need for planning out crime (Judith D. Feins 1997). Modern cities are giving increasingly complex safety challenges which lead to the need for crime prevention actions to be taken. Combining physical changes with programs to empower community members could be done to create livable communities. As said in the second generation of crime prevention strategies, crime reduction depends on community effort (Carmen.N 1997)

Aim

To analyze how community participation techniques contribute to crime reduction in urban residential areas.

Objective

To review the need for community planning, and examine existing safety conditions in urban residential areas.

Limitation

- Out of the various types of crimes, situational crimes are considered.
- Study is limited to three urban residential areas in Kollam

Research question

How our residential areas can be restructured through community participation?

Methodology

The stages involved in developing and implementing a community-based crime prevention strategy.

Stage 1

To conduct a community safety audit to identify problems and understand the community.

Outcome: Clarity regarding crime problems and an understanding of the characteristics of the community.

Stage 2

Developing planning strategies involving the community through a poster presentation.

Outcome: A crime and violence prevention strategy.

CPTED planning process for a multi-family housing community.

The major aim of this process is to create communication between planners and the residents. To improve community participation, it includes the distribution of flyers to every housing unit after each meeting. This contains the description of the overall project and information on CPTED, and information about the results of the last meeting and future plans.

The SARA process of problem-solving

SCANNING

- Identifying, defining, and investigating an already existing issue.
- Identifying the residents who will be involved in the problem-solving.
- Deciding on the meetings and activities that are required for problem-solving and creating a framework for working.

ANALYSIS

- Meetings with the community members to make them understand the problem and the goals and objectives of the process defined.
- Collection and analysis of information about the issue.
- Evaluation of the relation between the issues and environmental conditions.

RESPONSE

- Establishing the goals that need to be developed through the implementation of CPTED strategies.
- Identifying alternative strategies for implementing goals.
- Evaluating the social, political, legal, financial, or technological needs for implementing each strategy.
- Selecting the most appropriate strategies, creating and adopting a plan that identifies certain strategies, defining financial requirements, assigning duties for implementation, outlining a framework for plan implementation, and establishing an index of success.
- Putting the most feasible measures that are to be taken in order.
- A combination of responsible, short-term improvement and long-term investment is needed.

ASSESSMENT

- Monitoring the progress relative to the indicators of success specified in step 10.
- Deciding if the process needs to be repeated due to lack of progress on the emergence of new problems (Kruger 2001).

Case studies

Community-based Crime Prevention in South Africa

The project included Crime-mapping involving community members to suggest solutions for the identified Crime, Participatory process by local government officials or police officers, workshops, methods to assist the participants in understanding issues, cause and environmental factors related to crime and crime prevention, Perceptions of safety; through a resident's cognitive map exercise (T. Kruger 2008).

Activity support - Stakeholder's involvement in providing safety in crime zones

Crime prevention involving the community, agencies, groups, businesses, and individuals develops programs to make safer neighborhoods. Community-based crime prevention brings together many local stakeholders to focus their energies on developing designs to improve community safety while building a sense of connection and belonging among residents (Bania 2012).

Community-based Crime Prevention in South Africa

Crime mapping involving community members to suggest solutions for the identified crime. The individual participants had the opportunity to make contributions and to express themselves.

This process is appropriate for use in poorer communities, where people have to travel on foot through potentially dangerous areas. It has a focus on crime types that are committed in public areas where the nature of the physical environment may facilitate opportunities for crime and offending activity (TINUS KRUGER 2008).

Study area selection

Figure 1 Methodology used for study area selection

Source: Generated by author 2018

National Crime Records Bureau for the year 2015 said out of the 53 cities listed in that category, Kollam has the highest “crime rate” with maximum reporting of cases, mostly assaults, rioting, murder and homicide (deccanchronicle.com 2016). The NCRB statistics show that Kollam city has a population of 11.1 lakh and that when compared to 13,257 crimes, puts the crime rate at 1,194.3 (Pereira 2016). Kollam also recorded 172 incidents of assault on women, Police in the city also registered 217 cases of rioting (political reasons) (Varma 2016).

Figure 2 Crime statistics of Kollam Source: kollampolice.gov.in

For the maintenance of law and order 16 Kollam City Police Unit is subdivided into 3 Sub Divisions, out of which under Kollam subdivision there is 7 police wings.

Step 7 of methodology-

Police wing	Total IPC crime	Total SLL crime	Total crime
Kollam East Police wing	1120	3055	4175
Pallithottam	1289	929	2218
Kollam West(Ward 51 ; Tangasery)	888	1611	2499
Anchalummoodu(Ward 6 ;Kureepuzha)	1134	1444	2578
Sakthikulangara	772	1794	2566
Traffic Police	2059	2010	4069
Eravipuram	749	2117	2866
Kilikolloor(Ward 22 ;Chathinakulam)	947	2055	3002
Chathannoor	1117	1414	2531
Kottiyam	1006	2337	3343
Paravoor	910	1409	2319
Parippally	1005	1614	2619
Karunagappally	928	3767	4695
Oachira	690	2131	2821
Chavara	1402	2179	3581
Chavara Thekkumbhagom	800	1366	2166

Figure 3 Details of total number of IPC and SLL crimes in Kollam Corporation area

Source: DCRB Kollam

From all these information Three neighbourhoods were selected for the study purpose; one form least crime-oriented neighbourhood and two from crime-oriented neighbourhood. The selected neighbourhoods are:

Area 1- CHATHINAMKULAM, KILIKOLLOR, KOLLAM

- Household = appr.900people
- 300 dwelling units

- Site area=48404 m sq. (12 acre); density 75persons/acre (medium density).
- Lies informal, separate.
- Proximity to infrastructure (transit facilities 150 m).

Crime situation

The data from the Kilikollor police wing suggest that the area faces a number of riots(political)since 2016 and also two communal groups residing here cause conflicts. The crimes were recorded in IPC section 299 -376 which includes: Hurt to the human body, Missing cases, Narcotic cases that were too much under NDPS (Narcotics Drugs Psycho Traffic Substance Act), high suicide rates, theft and snatching, cheating cases. Also, there are nooks and corners which makes it difficult to identify people hiding.

Area 2 - KUREEPUZHA WEST, ANCHALUMMOODU, KOLLAM

- Residential houses = 479
- Households =(around)1900 people.
- 10 acres is taken for study.
- Medium density (density 75persons/acre).
- Lies informal, separate surrounded by the river on 3 sides so access to this area is less, crimes happen within Kureepuzha.
- Proximity to infrastructure- bus services are there but take ½ hour to reach the city due to the presence of a water body.

Crime situation

From 2012 many POCSO cases (sexual assault towards children) and rape cases were registered in the Anchalumood wing. IPC section included about 32-35 cases/month. Narcotics and drug cases and youth crimes are common here. Kureepuzha is one of the crime-oriented residential areas which lie as a peninsula. The crimes noted include assaults, accidents, crimes against women, riots cheating, political issues, and drug issues. There were around 5-10 Suo Moto cases (drinking, drug and public space, public nuisance) per day and 20 to 30 crime cases(IPC cases, hurt to the human body, murder).

Area 3- THANGASERRY

- 6.5 acres of area is taken for study.
- Residential houses under delineation= 527
- Household =(around)2500 people.
- High density (density 300-500persons/Ha).
- This area lies next to the city center and is highly populated.
- Proximity to all infrastructure facilities.

Crime situation

The data from the Kollam west police wing suggest that the Thangaserry region is facing from comparatively lower crime rate. Most of them are high professionals and high-income people. But individual conflicts might occur.

Method

The methods incorporated are as follows:

Non-participant observation/visual audit

To understand the physical characteristics of the study area through personal observations. The basic method, similar to a CPTED audit, is simply to walk around or drive around an area, making observations of conditions that are indicative of crime, disorder, and other threats to safety (real or perceived).

Interviewing, incorporating community participation

The sampling technique used here is “Opportunity Sampling” was participants who are both accessible and willing to take part are targeted. The major strength is that this method is easy to carry out and the drawback is that the consequent sample may not be represented as it could be subjected to changes.

Safety audit

The basic idea is to look at neighborhoods and identify areas where one feels unsafe and determine why they feel unsafe (What is the lighting like? Would anyone hear you if you yelled for help? What improvements would you like to see?).

Steps include:

1. Assessing the site to identify the reasons that affect the feelings of safety of the society.
2. Involving a group of people walking around a defined area, with each one writing their individual feelings down for later analysis.
3. Participants are given an overview of the purpose of the audit before undertaking it, but there will be a lack of professional input during the audit.
4. Safety audits can be conducted at differing times of the day and night using the same groups.
5. The end results of a Safety Audit may include suggestions of solutions for issues that are identified as having a negative impact on safety.
6. Safety Audit introduces a detailed subjective interpretation of the environment from the view of particular user groups (women, youth, people with disabilities), who may see an area differently (Coe 2005)

Onsite Audit

To measure the existing condition of the area based on the residents' opinions on various Environmental Design components used for Crime Prevention.

1. 30 respondents were randomly selected from each residential area located in Chathinamkulam, Kureepuzha, and Thagasherry, Kollam.
2. First a pilot survey with stakeholders was done for each area.
3. The study involves an understanding of attitude and sense of responsibility towards the respondents' residential area.
4. A face-to-face interview approach was used for the purpose of this study to ensure that the respondents fully understood the questions (residents were able to point out conditions that they interpret as signs of crime, disorder, and threat).
5. The survey was done for a period of one week, between 9 am until 5 pm.
6. Duration of 5 to 10 minutes was required for each respondent. In order to avoid any confusion or misunderstanding, the author explained the purpose of the study undertaken.
7. 8. The measurement of elements of the environment was based on referring crime prevention parameters.
8. 9. Community involved the process where the various crime prevention parameters were explained to each of them and their suggestions about those were considered.

Sample and respondent details

Chathinamkulam

The study involved more female respondents (57%) when compared to male respondents (43%) with a majority of the respondents being in the 30s to 40s age range group.

Kureepuzha

Similar to Chathinamkulam this involved more female respondents (57%) when compared to male respondents (43%) with a majority of the respondents being in the 40s to 60s age range group.

Thangaserry

The study involved more female respondents (63%) when compared to male respondents (37%) with a majority of the respondents being in the 25s to 35s, 45s to 60s age range group.

Figure 4 Site audit at Chathinamkulam | **Source: Generated by author 2018**

Figure 5 Site audit at Chathinamkulam | **Source: Generated by author 2018**

The safety audit survey was done focusing on the major 5 parameters derived from various situational crime prevention strategies. The opportunity survey included different people of all age groups and gender.

Safety audit (opportunity sapling)					
Name		Gender	Age	Marital status	
NATURAL SURVEILLANCE					
1	Does your property have rear entry?		yes	No	
2	Is your fencing height below 1.2m/does your wall have any openings?		yes	No	
3	Can you predict escape routes/is it difficult?		Yes	No	Map
4	Does your front garden hinder visibility?		yes	No	
5	Do you feel your place is safe for pedestrian walk?		Yes	No	
6	Is there sufficient lighting next to entrance?		Yes	No	
7	Are the child play areas visible from your house?		Yes	No	
8	Is kids usually accompanied from school?		Yes	No	
9	Does your house over look street?		Yes	No	
10	Do you have good quality street lighting?		Yes	No	
11	Does trees or bushes obscure lighting near the house?		Yes	No	
12	Are there hedges or bushes planted near window?		Yes	No	
13	Is it dangerous to walk alone at night?		Yes	No	
ACCESS CONTROL					
1	Do vagrants trespass your property?		Yes	No	
2	Does a pedestrian alley lead to your house?		Yes	No	Map
3	Is your rear private garden adjacent to neighbors?		Yes	No	
4	Do you think anyone can trespass your property without being seen by others?		Yes	No	
5	Do you think your house lack natural surveillance?		Yes	No	Map
TERRITORIAL REINFORCEMENT					
1	Do you incorporate target hardening measures (grill/dogs)?		Yes	No	
2	Is your property being used as a short cut?		Yes	No	
3	Do you see people hanging out near your plot?		Yes	No	Map

4	Do you care locking your gate when your go somewhere/at night?	Yes	No	
5	Does your property have a clearly defined boundary?	Yes	No	
ACTIVITY SUPPORT				
1	Is there good police patrolling there?	Yes	No	
2	Is there any local resident group activities?	Yes	No	
3	Do you have some conflicts with neighbors?	Yes	No	
4	Do you think strangers help u in danger?	Yes	No	
5	Do you trust everyone in your neighborhood?	Yes	no	
MAINTENANCE				
1	Does your wall have graffiti/poster?	Yes	No	Map
2	Do you see waste dumped near your property?	Yes	No	
3	Is your neighborhood noisy at times?	Yes	No	
4	Have you seen anyone drinking alcohol/play cards?	Yes	No	
5	Do you feel unsafe near abandoned plots?	Yes	No	

	11 Jan-2 Feb	2Feb – 23 Feb	23Feb – 8 Mar
Preliminary site visit			
Safety audit and community survey		WORKSHOP - 1	
Discussion of issues with community people and hearing their suggestions			WORKSHOP-2

Table 1 - Safety Audit check-list

Source: (Coe 2005) (Committee 2013)

Table 1 The stages and steps involved in developing and implementing a community-based crime prevention strategy.

Source: Generated by author, 2018.

Cognitive mapping

Workshop 1

Creation of a crime hot spot map with the help of residents

- i) Selection of people, persons or groups who are the residents of the place and have time and willing to participate in opportunity map exercise.
- ii) Explained the purpose of exercise and initiated a discussion on various locations within the neighborhood which were crime hot spots, asked about their personal opinion of the place.
- iii) Marked down places on the map and I explained the map to people (stakeholders) and asked them to identify locations where they feel unsafe.
- iv) I asked them the places they frequently visited also and places least visited and the frequency of visits to hot spots with or without company.
- v) Asked residents about any previous crime occurrences of this place and how much did it vary?

Common questions asked during the audit:

- What are the causes of fear of crime?
- What all could have been done to modify the present situation?
- What do all the residents do to bring up a positive image to the neighborhood?
- Asked about what all you feel to have been done for improving safety in the neighborhood and noting their suggestions (Authorgenerated 2018).

Figure 6 Stakeholder creating crime spot map at Chathinamkulam

Source: Generated by author, 2018.

Figure 7 Stakeholder creating crime spot map at Kureepuzha

Source: Generated by author, 2018.

Cognitive mapping exercise results

Cognitive mapping done by a women stakeholder indicates more pockets of land to the interior of the site was unsafe Senior citizens marked interior open abandoned spaces which are lacked surveillance as crime hot spots. School students mapped vacant land as crime hotspots; they said there is no delineation between public and private spaces in certain places. Hence there is a need for addressing both the built environment as well as social conditions.

Survey result analysis

The findings of the survey audit data were analyzed and found that the areas lacked natural surveillance mainly due to unmaintained overgrown vegetation; people had fear of crime to go out at night. There were issues relating to the bad quality street lighting. Fortress mentality was another notable character of these residential areas. Lack of proper definition between public and private spaces is another issue seen. Most residential areas lacked local residents' group activities. Most of them agreed to the fact that there are many antisocial activities such as drug

issues and alcohol consumption happening in suburban residential areas. The presence of narrow alleyways has created some safety issues and most people had fear to pass through. There was a lack of definition of spaces and one of the residents suggested the need for pedestrian pathways. Some people had the opinion that the police patrolling was not sufficient hence there has to be better people-police participation to meet the safety needs. Many places were left unmaintained hence, creating community spaces on unmaintained grounds can induce a sense of ownership and people will take care of those places. Community clean-up is a method that can improve the interaction between residents.

Workshop 2

Discussion of issues with community people and hearing their suggestions.

This was done through a poster presentation informing residents of the need for spatial planning in their locality and the importance of community interaction to reduce the fear of crime. For that, the author visited the residential areas for poster presentation where the author discussed the present situation of the area and what all could be done to ensure safe living among the residents. Various examples of crime prevention techniques used around the world were presented. Their suggestions, ideas, and views were considered. The discussion was concentrated around small kiosks, teashops where normally the people would gather.

Figure 8 Poster | Source: Generated by author, 2018

Figure 9 Poster presentation at Chathinamkulam

Source: Generated by author, 2018

Figure 10 Poster presentation at Kureepuzha

Source: Generated by author, 2018

Findings and suggestions

There were issues of anti-social activities like drug and alcohol use in public places. It could be reduced by delivering youth services like mural arts programs, school holiday programs. There is a need to improve the relationship between the local police and the community. In most of the residential areas, there are no local resident group activities. Due to reduced community interaction, many spaces within the neighborhood are left unmaintained, those places could be utilized for creating community spaces, or community clean-ups or creation of recreational opportunities can be incorporated. There are trust issues among neighbors which can be solved by community-based events such as social interaction programs (Active 24 hours a day by Jane Jacob); creation of neighborhood associations and inducing development by linking institutions to neighborhoods (like a park investment). Promote proper maintenance and management through a wide range of social activities in public spaces. The image of the place has to be maintained by removing the faded posters, worn displays, etc. Each individual has to be conscious about the cleanliness of their own surroundings.

Conclusion

To tackle crime effectively, communities need to be consulted on the problems they face and how to tackle them. There is an increase in the need for adopting evidence-based, consultative, and participatory approaches to preventing and reducing crime. Incorporating stakeholders can only give us the right idea of what all innovations need to be made and how effectively they can be developed. Conducting workshops during auditing could help people contribute their part in decision-making. Understanding people and considering their viewpoints is hence important for any spatial/social planning process.

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Cpted in hospitals: is it a distant dream? - Dr. Prakash Swaminathan and Dr. Angel Rajan Singh

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Abstract

CPTED is relatively a new concept in Indian Healthcare systems. It is more of a corrective measure which is instituted rather than the preventive one. This leads to retrofitting of various structures on a later date thereby disturbing the architecture and the aesthetics of the healthcare organization. AIIMS is the largest tertiary government hospital in India and is on a mammoth expansion to the tune of Rs 15000 Crores by way of a master plan project. A need was felt to incorporate the principles of CPTED into the master plan. By way of Focussed Group Discussions and Brainstorming sessions, a checklist of the various elements to be incorporated into the masterplan to feature the principles of CPTED. While doing so, it had to be kept in mind that introducing CPTED for Hospitals have its own challenges as the environment of Hospitals is different from other dwellings. The paper aims at identifying the same too. This will go a long way by incorporating these ideas in the master plan at the initial stages itself and make it a part of the Integrated Project Delivery rather than retrofitting these structures at a later date.

Keywords: CPTED , Hospital and Healthcare Facilities , Hospital Crimes , Checklist, Integrated Project Delivery

What is already known about this chapter?

The IAHSS (The International Association for Healthcare Security and Safety Organisation) has specifically mentioned various guidelines to be considered in the planning and designing of a healthcare facility in detail in their recent (3rd Edition) of the book , Security Design Guidelines for Healthcare Facilities.

What does this study add?

Lots of scholarly articles are available on the topic of CPTED in Buildings and Residential complexes. There are very less articles specifically on the subject of CPTED in Hospitals and as to why to implement them. This article attempts to find an answer for these questions and solutions for the same and prepare a checklist which could act as a blueprint in the future.

Introduction

The Oxford Dictionary defines Crime as “An action or omission which constitutes an offence and is punishable by law.”(Oxford English Dictionary, n.d.)

The International Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED) Association defines CPTED as “A multi-disciplinary approach of crime prevention that uses urban and architectural design and the management of built and natural environments. CPTED strategies aim to reduce victimization, deter offender decisions that precede criminal acts, and build a sense of community among inhabitants so they can gain territorial control of areas, reduce crime, and minimize fear of crime. ”(The International Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design Association, n.d.) ‘No physician, however conscientious or careful, can tell what day or hour he may not be the object of some undeserved attack, malicious accusation, black mail or suit for damages.... (Assaults upon Medical Men. JAMA. 1892; 18:399-400.)

Violence against doctors and other healthcare workers are on the increase in the entire world and India is no different in this scene. As per researcher, Kanjaksha Ghosh, most of the incidents of violence are in the casualty and ICU. (Ghosh, 2018).Reasons as enumerated are the emotional nature of the environment, political interference, lack of communication, etc. As per a study being conducted by the Indian Medical Association, about 75% of the doctors have experienced violence in some or the other form in our country. India stands a bit apart from the crowd as in most of the cases, the incidences of crime against healthcare workers are committed by the relatives or bystanders of the patients, rather than the patients themselves. In most of the

Western countries, the system of relatives / bystanders accompanying the patients is comparatively lesser. In India, it is more of a social and moral obligation of people known to the patient to accompany the patient and show extreme concern and affection to the patient during his need.

Various codes are present in hospital to help disseminate the action and Standard operating procedures to be followed when any sort of mishap happens in the hospital for eg a patient having collapsing as an effect of a cardiac event , fire , theft , abduction etc. Code purple is the code in which Healthcare professionals could be held hostage. Code pink stands for infant abduction in hospital. These are the important codes in hospitals which stand for various crimes generally occurring in hospital set ups.

Though various methods have been formulated by many authors (Indla Ramasubba Reddy, Jateen Ukrani, Vishal Indla, 2019) (Nagpal, 2017)(Raveel & Schoenmakers, 2019) for the prevention of crime in hospitals, not much importance is given to the engineering part for crime prevention.

Aim

To find out what are the various CPTED parameters which can be incorporated in a Hospital Setting

Objectives

- i) To find out the reasons why CPTED in Hospital settings are different?
- ii) To find out the nature of crimes in a hospital settings
- iii) To suggest corrective measures to introduce CPTED in a hospital setting?
- iv) To chalk out a project management technique to introduce CPTED in hospital.

Why is a Hospital a different place to incorporate the principles of CPTED?

Hospital is a matrix organisation in which healthcare workers are working in an emotionally charged up setting.(Heyhoe et al., 2016). Patient safety practices also have to be followed in a hospital setting. Various building principles being followed for CPTED in the way of laying of barricades, hurdles, aesthetic gardens etc. cannot be incorporated for a healthcare institute as we have to keep in mind that there should be very less hindrance in the movement of the

patient, healthcare workers, security and healthcare attendants. At the same time, patient privacy is also of utmost importance to protect his / her modesty.

Recently the Government mandated the use of CCTV Cameras in the patient wards for the treatment of patients undergoing treatment for the pandemic of COVID-19. This order was met with mixed response by the healthcare workers from the ethical point of view. While the use of CCTV helped in the remote monitoring of patients being treated for a very severely infective illness, there was also a fear of patient privacy being jeopardised and also a dissatisfaction as it was perceived this was a means to monitor the work output of the doctors and paramedics who were otherwise famished and tired by treating doctors with the personal protective equipments (PPE) on themselves.

What are the different types of crimes which can take part in a hospital?

- (i) While most of the literature search zeroes in on attack on healthcare workers as the crime occurring on healthcare workers in a hospital settings, we cannot be oblivious of the various other crimes.
- (ii) Infant abduction and kidnapping especially in a country like India where infertility is on the rise and also the wish to have a male child cannot be forgotten.
- (iii) The authors wish to highlight another important crime which otherwise increased during the pandemic. It was that of theft of personal belongings of the patients. It was very difficult at times to trace the culprits, even though there were CCTV footages available because most of the Healthcare workers were in PPEs.
- (iv) The introduction of the concept of Green buildings for hospitals are also known to compromise the privacy of the patients. In an effort to reduce energy consumptions, huge glass windows in the hospital has surely yielded results. It is also accepted that with the increase in the sunlight and exposure to the surroundings and visibility there has been a positive effect on the mental status of the patients (Ulrich et al., 2018). However the same is known to compromise the privacy (Leading to crimes like Voyeurism) especially of the wards in the ground and the first floors of the hospitals and especially at night time when the lighting inside the wards are more as compared to the lighting outside.
- (v) We cannot go against the principles of designing of hospitals and thus we have to have emergency care areas and wards generally for psychiatric patients in these floors. But these are the departments where the patients are generally not in a position to take care of themselves and thus need privacy.

- (vi) Mob Attacks are also known especially during the death of any VIP who has lots of followers or pseudo- followers.
- (vii) At times for reasons including political motives, such mob mentality can go in for arson, looting etc. The Mumbai attack of 2008 wherein bomb explosions and attacks at the Cama and Alless hospital is well known. Holding hospital hostage for ransom is a mechanism which cannot be negated.
- (viii) Suicide is another crime (though there is conflict between IPC Section 309 which criminalises attempt to suicide and the Mental Healthcare Act, 2017 which bars prosecution) which can occur in hospital settings. It would be highest amongst patients seeking psychiatric treatment.

Principles which have to be borne in mind while Thinking of CPTED for Hospital

- (i) Crime can be discouraged if the following parameters are kept in mind:- (The International Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design Association, n.d.)
 - a) Ensure Natural and Passive surveillance
 - b) Ensure Territoriality and discourage criminal activity: - Even in a government set up, notices against vandalism should be clearly projected.
 - c) Ensure Access Control.
- (ii) CPTED works on the following Principles:-
 - a) Physical Security: - Strong and Quality constructions of the Hospitals to withstand attacks.
 - b) Surveillance:- By use of CCTV Cameras , Access restricted to those entering the CCTV room, Authority for those who can use the footages- SOPs to be framed for the same, Telephone numbers of the control room of the Hospital at prominent places which can be dialled in case of any crime occurring and thus help can be initiated.
 - c) Movement control: - High levels of through movements should not be permitted. Restriction of access will help in crime control.
 - d) Management and Maintenance :- Complete maintenance of the surrounding areas should be done , so that there is good vision of these areas with the naked eye as well as in CCTVs
 - e) Defensible spaces: - Defining high access areas and imposing restrictions on trespassers.

- (iii) The Physical Environment can be manipulated in the following ways to reduce crime:-
- Natural :- Including Basic security and behavioural provisions
 - Organised :- By Security
 - Mechanical: - Incorporation of Security Hardwares.

How to incorporate CPTED in Hospitals?

- The hospital which we work in is a large tertiary hospital in Northern India and we are on the verge of a mammoth expansion to the tune of Rs 15000 Crores . CPTED is a new concept which we are interested in incorporating in our constructions. Hence, a focussed group discussion (FGD) was conducted to chalk out the checklist for the introduction of CPTED in future constructions of the Hospital.
- The members of the FGD were
 - 4 members from the Department of Hospital Administration who had an average of 5 years' service (minimum of 3 years) experience in Project Management of Hospital buildings.
 - There were 4 members from the Engineering background with average of 10 years (minimum 7 years) experience in the field of Engineering of Hospitals.
 - Members from the security services being provided at hospital were also members of the hospital. Two members retired from the Armed Forces and employed as security consultants in our hospital and having an experience of security of five years in our hospital were incorporated.
- Rounds of the entire Hospital was taken after a FGD and areas and after detailed deliberation , different areas where the CPTED can be incorporated have been considered
- Based on various literature ,findings of the FGD, rounds of the hospital four rounds of brainstorming sessions were held . Based on these exercises, the following are the various areas in which CPTED can be introduced:-

Area Description

Security Staff Changing and Rest Room

In many of the Hospitals, it is the Security personnel (Either own or outsourced) who look into the safety of the Hospitals. But in very few cases have we taken into consideration the provision for their changing room, rest room and resting places during short breaks. The same should be incorporated into the designing of a hospital.

Entry of the Hospital

Preferably the entry and exit points (even if they are multiple) should be separate. In no case, should reverse movements be allowed. There should be enough barricades available to stop movement, if required in an emergency.

CCTVs

CCTVs should be placed at all vulnerable areas. CPTED also concentrates on the fear instilled in the minds of criminals looking out for performing a crime. This thus becomes a deterrent factor. Access to the CCTVs scrutiny centre should be very highly restricted. Access to the footage should be with the highest echelon of administration of the hospital.

Parking Areas Parking Areas for staff and visitors should be at separate areas with restricted access.

Building Management System and electronic methods of surveillance

Building Management system using the best software should be incorporated into the hospital buildings. This can help in cordon off the affected areas and restrict the damage done by miscreants. This can be very useful in cases of hostage like situation, abductions etc where the entire hospital or areas can be barricaded with the touch of a button.

(Jradi et al., 2021)

Intercoms

Public Address System

Intercoms with the control room numbers at all vulnerable places should be present. Adequate numbers of PA system which will help in calling for help and for issuing warnings.

Frosted / Filmed Glasses

Though the importance of Green buildings and Positive effect on patients cannot be negated, we need to also give importance to the patients' privacy. In view of this it is recommended that films on glass or frosting of the glass especially in vulnerable patient care areas be done. The use of blinds or curtains is discouraged because they are fomites –potential source of infection.

(Owen & Laird, 2020)(Ohl et al., 2012)

Locks

Push button locks for Toilets which can be opened from outside by a single key common to all the toilets is recommended. This will help in opening the door in case of any attempts of suicides in closed spaces like toilets.

Fire Extinguishers

It has become mandatory now a days to have the full Fire plan in place. The same should however be incorporated into a hospital building plan.

Generator Rooms

Quick restoration of electricity by means of generator in case of power failure.

VIP Patients / Well wishers

In order to prevent frenzied mobs, it is advisable to have a separate entry to the hospital (or alternatively staff access routes) to maintain harmony in the hospital environment.

Counselling/Prognostication Room

A separate room with minimum furniture and doors for easy access for escape of healthcare workers is recommended for explaining the prognosis of the patient and counsel the relatives in cases of bad prognosis. This will help in alleviating the hostility before any unacceptable news.

CBRN Areas

Areas which have a potential to be used as crime locations wherein Chemical Biological Radiological and Nuclear items / equipments are stored should be in highly secluded areas with strict controls.

Street Lighting with back ups

Good street lightings with back up by solar powered / generators is required.

Maintenance

Continuous maintenance of the areas by preventing shrubs and foliage.

At the inception levels landscaping should be planned. Though importance should be given for aesthetics, we should ensure that trees that have a potential of overgrowing shouldn't be planted

very near to the windows thus obstructing vision and lighting. These may also conceal criminal activities.

Ambient Conditions

Ensuring proper HVAC systems in the Hospital will lessen the existing mental and physical discomfort of patients and relatives.

(Shajahan et al., 2019)(MohammadiGorji et al., 2021)

Installing Privacy and security Screens at Emergency

This will protect the staff from violent actions and also help in preventing infections. Confidentiality is also maintained.

Pharmacies and registration counters

Clear and unobstructed view of pharmacy entrance and registration counters and hardening the transaction window and surrounding wall with protective material

The above mentioned points are some of the ways in which CPTED can be implemented in hospitals. Building management System is one which allows to tackle almost all of the issues. CPTED is not a panacea, and it does not guarantee that the hospital is not safe from any crime or a fear of getting caught in crime creeps into the mind, but it can surely reduce the incidence. It can help create supportive physical environments for social and economic initiatives.

Integrated Project Management

- i) Integrated Project management is the coordination of all elements of a project. This includes coordinating tasks, resources, stakeholders, and any other project elements, in addition to managing conflicts between different aspects of a project, making trade-offs between competing requests, and evaluating resources.
- ii) This should also incorporate the security point of view into constructions. It is a well-known fact that retrofitting of structures can be difficult and a costly affair (Hakim Choudhary et al., 2020).
- iii) Hence the planning stage should have a integrated approach and incorporate security personnel at the planning and designing step itself. Thomas A. Smith, President and Principal Consultant at Healthcare Security Consultants and former IAHS President states that, "Security impacts every area of the hospital from the parking lot in. The

initial planning and conceptual design phase of all newly constructed or renovated health care facility should include a security vulnerability assessment led by a qualified security professional.”

Conclusion

CPTED in Hospitals: Is it a Distant Dream?

The answer is NO. It is not. It requires the incorporation of certain changes and the eyes and vision of true leader who is ready to accept the importance of this concept. For our hospitals, after discussions, we find that it is not difficult to be introduced at a starting concept.

Once introduced and validated by professionals, including security professionals, CPTED for Hospitals is not a distant dream. It only requires the effort of ideas to be incorporated at the planning stage itself and supervision during execution.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST: - None

Source of funding: - Nil

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Applied Situational Intelligence by Dynamics in Human Context: a functional alternative for security and sustenance in autonomous facilities - K Ravi Kumar Reddy and Srikonda Ramesh

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Abstract

Suggestive architectural design principles evolved to create built environments to care for crime prevention using CPTED methodologies by designers to build the secured living and working spaces. And by pure design philosophy, these may simply be an applicability to greenfield projects. In fact, there are more active and unorganized prebuilt environments around the world, and their active usage is very high in percentage. The humanity has come to the age of digital support on every endeavor that is round the clock and in realtime with varied range of applications, starting from communications to static as well as dynamic facilities aligned with habitat.

The principal ideology to CPTED, on the premise of digitalization, is necessitating system enhancements in approach of treating the humans as centric to services and influenced by facilities in use. It shall not only be security through provisioned services but also the assets and facilities of ownership by an individual or group. The security shall be treated as a domain of importance which is dependent on other critical components in the spatial action. And human context is always dynamic which will have a serious influence about the assets and facilities of build environment. Ever-changing contextual upbuild of human is single as well as ubiquitous in groups.

The social cliques are the foundation of understanding the level of interactions while the location services to drive for details in analysis of proximity in facilities. Thus, design reasoning of a policy driven context centric system is very complex. The policy generates variety of contextual observations, whether the space occupation is individual or groups against security measurements by constant processing of data on issues pertaining to environment and

facilities through time. A greater systemic integration with variety on both passive and active models about variables among environment would only provide problem resolutions.

It is by application of measurable capacities about installed spatial hierarchy and their proposition against the contextual influence. This paper discusses the implementation theories in reasoning of sensing, process modelling, policies and platform architecture. The system architecture shall determine variety of data acquisition points and policy models on applications against supporting the security. Sustenance of humans shall be of great priority with all encountered dynamism in contexts against time and situations.

Keywords: Concurrent Context, Data Analytics, Internet of Things, Location Services, Policy Models, Service Proliferation Context, Situational Awareness, Situational Intelligence, Social Cliques, Ubiquitous Context.

Introduction

The crime against fellow humans as well as the occupied facilities is a very common phenomenon. And these incidences are attributable to various conditions among offenders. Broadly these revolve around inequalities of various kinds that exists in social strata. Since the prevention and control is a global activity through governing systems, local methods in attention to incidents be deployed with necessary automation in prevention of crime occurrences. These applications must follow the space design in the way to exhibit the surveillance of the spatial components that are either in active use or hibernated buffers. It is not only the survival of humans from crime but also the facilities since these are synonymous to human privacy, security and comfort. The design of spaces, traditionally, has evolved only on these three fundamental principles of creativity.

Early humans survived the predatory uncertainty from other wild, and architectural design of spaces have gone long way to aesthetical appeal while creating secured envelopes and also categorization to the way of living and working spaces. This knowledge of universal design ideology of space organization for a purpose is thus translated through possibilities of intrusions by miscreants into the facility establishment. CPTED (sep-ted as *sep-ted*) argues that the building of safer environments are the enablers in improving quality of life (Atlas, 2013), and principles applied are constraints on methodologies in architectural space design.

Appropriate approach in addressing the vulnerability is by ‘problem seeking’ before the ‘problem solving’ (Atlas, 2013), a strategic approach is assessment on prioritizing observations on the vulnerabilities to building during the design preparations. However, there are buildings which have been in purposive use before CPTED applied through design. Conducting a separate retrofitting risk assessment is a critical requirement for covering vulnerabilities about exposures to crime in the space. The SARA (scanning, analysis, response and assessment) process becomes handy to kickstart deployment of security policy since one type (*at the least*) of a crime data is available (Lawrence, 2018) against the profile of target space.

“No one would have believed, in the last years of the nineteenth century, that human affairs being watched keenly and closely by intelligences greater than man’s and yet as mortal as his own; that as men busied themselves about their affairs they were scrutinized and studied, perhaps almost as narrowly as a man with microscope might scrutinize the transient creatures that swarm and multiply in a drop of water.”

H. G. Wells, War of the Worlds, 1898.

A newer dimension of CPTED is about the dynamics of change in quality occupation of space and temporal variability due to diverse consciousness of individuals. The human context is an authoritative constituent while individual or group in facility access and usage. Therefore, security dimensioning must be assessed from the perspective of covering the human as an element for protection against threats, crime and disasters.

The defense against the facilities in the built space and neighborhoods is less significant when the occupancy state is inactive. The attention to the value of human life and material loss are the larger objectives. The CPTED principles shall be restructured to methodology in addressing the human as the center of all the proposals which is deterministic of individual traits. This is by shaping the slave systems surrounded to cover the risk of all earthly vulnerabilities and configurations of comforts (USA Patent No. US 9,253,618 B2, 2016).

This translates to understanding the situations in engaging the variable human context. Application of intelligence is the most relevant security activation to cover impending risks while dynamically observing every individual as independent involvement.

The target serviceable context may well be with multitude of dimensions in real scenarios of space occupancy. This activity would remeasure the state of dynamics in case any vulnerability. The importance in building an ecosystem for CPTED as extension to base platform of Smarter Planet (Palmisano, 2008) is ideal for dealing with crime mitigation and handling vulnerabilities for sustenance.

Fig.1. Service provisioning process (Original).

The involvement of two most important subject areas critical for the implementation of an efficient CPTED by policy are 1) the facility management and 2) the transition management across facilities.

Facilities Enable the Categorization to Transitions

Building is purely a static structure, but complex most relations to social being in the space to treat usage as a machine though (Hillier, 2007). The deployed devices among facilities are configurable/ modifiable in operative microenvironments, but to the limited extent of purposive use of the space. But the transitions across the multiple aligned spaces is dynamic as and when becomes operational by inhabitants/ users. Traversals across the transitions in encountered spaces by an individual are highly evolutionary and temporal. Though, some states are repetitive and many may be of new definition and ever changing. On the time scale, transitions are always in a harmonic model of convenience from one end to another. This brings the interpreted dynamism in interfacing with space and facilities by humans.

Types of Spaces and Evolution of Usage							
Physiological State	Private	Family	Neighbourhood	Crowd	Neighbourhood	Common	Individual
Occupancy Nature	Highly Secluded	Structure Organized	Organized Social	Unknown Social		Organized Temporary	Work Isolated
Risk Vulnerably	Very Low	Low	Medium	High	High	Medium	Low
Transition Property	Secured	Secured	Compromised				Secured

Table 2. Organization of built spaces at transitional security attitudes (Original).

The above description of transitions outlined in *Table.1* would get reorganized on basis of maturity in mitigating the vulnerability scenarios. Granular the variants in process models for discovering the dynamics of contextual behaviors against facilities and transitions, comprehensive would be the knowledge on mitigation of risk about security in various situations involving human interaction with spaces.

Human Context and Demand for Portfolio of Services

While converting the theory of sensing to devices, all spatial assets of purpose would need to be considered as embodied devices which are virtual in operations. Environmental sensing is

an integral part of these devices in support of required automation. This is to demystify the popular notion that sensing is a basis of automation. It is wrong. The assets in facility through devices are needing sensing extensions in enabling automation in their respective scope of operations (*Fig. 1*). Typical behavior of devices is again not independent in the facility, but synchronous with other devices deployed in fulfilment of facility. It is a primary condition in the need of maneuvering these on basis of human context in time. In a way, the calibration of multiple of devices in a facility shall consolidate to favorable service portfolio as modelled to support human temporal needs. The service ecosystem in a facility shall always be centric to human necessities and so the deployment as well as the enablement of devices.

Multiplicity of Human Context

Context is environment driven for survival of human as a biological being and there could be variety (Ashby, 2015) of collections. These are by macro and associative micro corrections to the embraced situations. The context also tends to have a higher influence of anthropological knowledge (Long, 2001) on social interfaces (*and certainly not physical integrations*). And this is a self-caused influence of trade-offs which has a definite impact on solicitation of the situational intelligence. The context has many application possibilities surrounded by humans and a digitally virtual and artificial consciousness (Cardon, 2018) always following in helping to bear with situations among;

- Personal communications managed through devices and become elements for data interfacing to context processing system.
- Built-up facilities that are supporting systems against appropriation of the context for utilities and space usage.
- Extended context also helps in processing the models for personal health as well as hazard mitigation. The preventive intelligence through passive situation understanding and corresponding association to target context of possible impact may be very much outside to context active facilities.
- Life critical applications of critical care etc. are of direct association to the context in handling the active situation demands.
- Mission critical dependencies by involving a predetermined model as accomplishment to time, and again to known facilities and beyond.

Following elaborative of definitions to 'context' is the original work by author¹, a **research FOAK**.

Concurrent Context: Once own behavioural background that is very selfish in situation management, truly to an individual attention, and with no facility compromise.

Ubiquitous Context: Attenuative to varying parameters on facility use while sharing the unions or optimizations through stakes of others in the group;

Fixed Permanent Ubiquitous, the context is omnipresent to user whether inside or outside to the common facilities. the context is omnipresent at fixed configurations gets updated to user context based on location of importance.

Fixed Temporary Ubiquitous, the context is omnipresent to user whether inside or outside the common facilities for a fixed duration of time.

Varying Permanent Ubiquitous, the context of a preconfigured case is permanent, but spatial changes across the time when influencing the group of users and their common situational awareness.

Varying Temporary Ubiquitous, constantly varying context and user the context is updated for situational awareness of varying omnipresent context, and this is temporary on spatial sense for some duration and the range of influence. participation of individual into the group context and at the same time attentive to exclusivity of Concurrent Context.

Service Proliferation Context: This is with exclusivity to CPTED and analysis to environmental updates on both facility users as well as the intrusions of anonymous, where the unknown scenario is also omnipresent along with legally associated contexts to facility or transition. The criminal activities are intrusions to active or inactive states of a determined context, where the changes in abnormalities are assessed on risk-based corrections, and all the original facility wise contexts are restored to normal. The application intent is to keep sniffing proactive corrections using mitigation alternatives in support of the legitimate contexts.

Knowing the extent of applicability, the context also could be of multiple kinds by definition (*described above*). Critical course correction of process preparations/ analysis is performed to scope and limits since the commonness in the physical environment and filled with biological uniformity. Thus, context engagement shall be within the primordial limits of every individual.

Global Adaptation of Situational Intelligence

Comparing to the army combat situations – ‘every soldier is a sensor’ (Larsen, 2018), which is quite different from the general purpose. The facilities encountered by combat personnel may be very much alien to their orderliness, for which the control instruments and devices are deployed for temporary use by the command. In the military terms, the facilities are by nature volatile and unknown to the action and command. In case of replicating the same purpose for a normal civilian in day-to-day living, the facilities are known and mapped with processes in adjusting to human requisites of time-n-usage.

Fig.2. Military and civilian engagements of situational awareness.

The space occupant is more passive in intelligence but the backend systems collecting critical information from known sources and seamlessly track/ ingest in performing data analytics for applicability to emerging/ encountered situations. Each situation is a mission for sake of management, and transformative in frequent changes to the convenience of a single person whether individual or sharing the space in groups (Refer to §4). Every sequence in mission modification, intelligence is gathered for tracking the behavioral patterns and those become applied rules on one or many repetitive engagements. And these rules are highly normalized/ rationalized enactment against a specific type of situation delivery and engagement. In information terms these are sessions with specific system process identity. And also bound to

have definite start and end time with delta duration which tend to give more knowledge in decision about the strength of applied rules against an individual type context.

IoT and Data Collaborative Environment

Internet of Things (IoT) is a probable launch platform for delivering the security to facilities in a scale involving to build various hierarchy levels of spatial scope. But it needs more appropriation to the systems requirements of situation analysis and data collection. While expectation of the situation delivery in almost realtime, many predetermined rules of context mapping would be near-realtime due to inherent and redundant properties while known experiences of space. In a general application framework of IoT, security management is an additional and pre-built capability, but very rudimentary in managing only a) facility access, 2) video surveillance from the command center, and etc. The situational awareness supportive applications would definitely require a very larger capacity and higher system performance.

Facilities Management is becoming smarter by virtue of digital disruptions (Streather, 2016), and tend improve the space efficiencies by means of; a) reliability, b) optimization, c) operational continuity, d) interfacing to complexity of space transitions, e) merging legacy and facilities expansions, d) maintenance of facilities, e) reporting and compliance, and etc. IoT with sufficient data analytics would perform evidence-based situation decisions which are difficult in traditional facilities management. And for taking care of 'Service Proliferation Context' (Refer to §4 box subheading '3' and §9 and subsection '1') and the surrounded processes, an IoT hosted virtual platform with sizing and performance segregated tenant only can deliver CPTED orientated security management (*many data elements may be shared between host IoT and CPTED subsystem*) for operationally covering not only facilities but also the inhabitants.

Fig.3. Situation engagement system and delivery of human context.

Data Requirements for Composition of the Context

Since the platform of IoT is data intensive with integration of collection, processing and decisions – the subset of context preparation and maintenance is very critical for success of situation upbuild. More source data types and interfaces would assist in effective composition to the context with richness to situation process and applicability. Substantial amount of human behavioral elements is needed to be present in the formalization of the context. The degree of influence of the context or tendency against a facility transformed processes is the key for appropriate situation management. The definition of data identity to passive and active interfaces is a priority understanding for divergent situation analysis. The contextual information is categorized quite differently at purpose and may form cross-referencing sets among data.

- Personal Identity: At least one of personal identity is expected to be shared with primary device which is instrumental in associating rest of the interfaces in the context.
- Location Services: Interface with either live location details from internet companies or local device that share details through an established facility related interface.
- Composition of Presence: Social Network Analysis (SNA) could provide some sense in the state of interests which may be personal but again location bound with social influence.
- User Groups: Again, SNA or the individual context update of the group members consolidate on availability of group in a common facility which is based on formation of presence in social cliques.
- Ecological Barriers: This may be a constant property in the context. It would always influence the comfort and security on known physiological deficiencies and physical threats.

Integrity Management of the Context

Fig.4. Integrity management process of the context to be up-to-date.

Sample Use cases

Unauthorized Intrusions, Anonymity

- a. Data Composition: RFID, video analytics, location analysis, crime type hierarchy i. trespass, ii. burglary, iii. vandalism, iv. property destruction, and v. physical harm.
- b. Data Process: a) access analysis, b) contextual updates of legal inhabitants, c) mapping of location to anonymous, and d) intension analysis.
- c. Decisions: a) spatial heat map of area under influence of anonymous, b) facility wise proximity analysis against intent of crime, c) mitigation plan of action/ crime isolation to cordoning-off the periphery of heat map.

Environmental Hazards, Flooding

- a. Data Composition: terrain analysis, location analysis, rainfall density, and types of facilities under vulnerability.
- b. Data Analysis: a) facility elevation, b) contextual updates of legal inhabitants, c) facility under inundations levels, and d) temporal analysis.

- c. Decisions: a) risk analysis on levels that can harm the life, b) plan of action on evacuations, c) flood water management, c) identify alternative of safer facilities, and d) deploy engineering to reduce the physical damage to facilities.

Description of Terminologies

Situational Awareness

Situation Awareness has been recognized as a critical, yet often elusive, foundation for successful decision-making across a broad range of situations, many of which involve the protection of human life and property, including law enforcement, aviation, air traffic control, ship navigation, health care, emergency response, military command and control operations, self-defense, and offshore oil and nuclear power plant management. Lacking or inadequate situation awareness has been identified as one of the primary factors in accidents attributed to human.

Situational Intelligence

Situational intelligence brings together business intelligence, operational intelligence and location intelligence. Data from every source is analyzed and visualized in a single solution to simplify decision-making. Situational Intelligence is a proven approach that unites data from across an organization to provide the context needed for fast, confident decision-making. Situational intelligence correlates, analyses and visualizes massive amounts of disparate data to identify the crucial few items that require attention. All types of data are useful in situational intelligence, including data from enterprise systems, operational systems (pumps, motors, etc.), IoT devices (meters, sensors, etc.) and external systems (weather, social media, traffic, fires, etc.).

Fig.5. Differentiation between Situational Intelligence and Situational

Conclusion

Digital has changed the way data is acquired, analyzed and applied to various situations concerning to humans. The interventions in design of spaces, keeping in view of security and surveillance of environment in built environment as suggested in the principles of CPTED also would go for redefinition. Thus, preparing the policies against the micro and macro hierarchy of involved territories of either static or dynamic to have been surrounded by humans in variety of contextual upbuild. The interfaced support of systems against ever changing human context in targeted space must be at par with military grade of command management. The maturity in security models shall cover the anticipation as well as runtime vulnerabilities against the reformulated contextual sets of either individual or groups. These are very complex in configurable aspects of occupied space by one or many at a given point of time. The foundations of policies in addressing such intricacies must start along architectural design of physical space or by plan renewing the assets in active usage. The formulated policies shall get converted to process models and supported by appropriate data analysis. The deployed situation management systems shall embrace the policies of isolating the vulnerabilities of exposure to either hazards or crimes against individuals/ groups and also their occupied space in realtime. The analysis of experiences in effectiveness of the situation delivery becomes definite feedback that is meant for process maturity. Advanced methods in feedback techniques can redefine and remold the processes. This system build can deliver self-fulfilling models that

would address the latest and renewed challenges in addressing the vulnerabilities of facility space in time.

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Environmental security design at building level and city level for crime prevention - Dhananjay Manthanwar , Chaganti Saibabu , Jagath Kumari Dungi

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Abstract

In this paper, the authors discuss the crime prevention through environmental design which includes natural surveillance, natural access control, territorial reinforcement, maintenance and management. CPTED principles have a huge scope of application in architecture, urban planning, and facility management. There is a need for crime prevention at public and private spaces such as houses, car parking, parks, and approach areas, bus stations, sidewalks, under bridges, public toilets, roads, offices, malls and hotels.

Keywords: CPTED, modern methods, measures for control, public safety, facility management.

Highlights: In this paper the applications of CPTED principles can be followed while planning and designing of buildings has been discussed. Mainly the authors made an attempt to improve safety and security of buildings for crime prevention.

Introduction

Crime prevention through environmental design, CPTED has a set of principles that works in preventing crime at various levels. Their application can ensure design of safe spaces for mankind. The CPTED principles can be implemented without obstructing the normal use of space. These strategies are economical and can be implemented with ease. The four principles of CPTED are discussed as follows (Guidebook of crime prevention through environmental design, 2003).

Natural Surveillance

The main objective of natural surveillance is to create greater number of people observing a place, which has threat of crime. Providing adequate windows, openings that are facing the place which has a threat of crime.

Natural access control

The main objective of natural access control is to stop unauthorized access in any public/private spaces. In public spaces this can be done by providing proper lighting, signage and entry barriers. In private spaces making channelized entrances and exits can reduce this crime.

Territorial Reinforcement

The main objective of territorial reinforcements is to restrict and provide barriers for movement in public and private spaces. By providing fences, paths, interactive art, clear cut boundaries between public and private spaces can be established.

Maintenance and Management

The Main objective of maintenance and management is to create an area which would not be targeted for the crime. Designing the spaces with right selection of materials and finishes such as selection of plants that do not obstruct sight lines.

Literature Review

- **Randy Clarke et al. (2010) carried out research on Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED) for Transit Facilities.** the author discusses the concepts and strategies for crime prevention for transit facilities that shall be incorporated while planning and design of transit facilities and its surrounding such as paths, stations.
- **Paul Cozens, and Terence Love. (2015) carried out research studies on Current status of crime prevention through Environmental Design (CPTED).** the author discusses how CPTED is spreading widely and the strategies are getting more popular. The strategies of the CPTED are an attractive option for individuals, communities, local, state and national governments and international organizations. To preserve its popularity, CPTED must persistently adapt to changes such as expanding urbanization, population densities and population diversity, modern advances and products, new ways of life, and emerging crime problems.
- **National Crime Prevention Council Singapore (2003) discussed about Crime prevention through environmental design.** In this author discuss the CPTED principles, basic design and management studies of spaces. Highlights regarding, how these principles can be applied in various developments such as industrial areas, schools and institutes private spaces such as offices, hotels etc. are also provided.

Methodology

In this paper we are going to discuss about the applications of CPTED principles. In discussions, the possible suggestions have been written down to adapt in public and private spaces. We can achieve it by understanding the design and management strategies.

Basic design and management strategies discusses about the elements involved in planning and design of the space, such that the space is safe for users and the intended purpose of space is fulfilled.

Basic design and management strategies

The four principles of CPTED can be applied in planning and design that is used to enhance security for the specific space.

- Provision of sufficient lighting,
- Minimized packed and isolated routes.
- Allowance for clear sight lines,
- Reduced isolation and entrapment.
- Mixed land use and activity generators.
- Overall improved design and built environment.

These strategies shall apply on site conditions, there may be some applications either or sometimes every strategy shall apply depending on space and functional requirements of the project.

Discussion

Discussion about various spaces in public and private environments and providing suggestions for improvements based on observations (Guidebook of crime prevention through environmental design, 2003).

Public housing

Common areas in apartments. (2020, October 22). [Photograph]. housing.com.

<https://housing.com/news/common-areas-in-apartments/>

Hidden areas should be avoided in stairs, corridors and lift lobbies. Places where avoiding hidden places is not possible, we can achieve it by using transparent materials such as glass. The access to individual buildings should have a clear sight line from the adjacent streets and apartments. Proper signage containing the street names and block numbers should be there within the development and should be visible from the public road.

Providing site maps at central locations can help the people during emergency services and it helps visitors to understand the location. Adequate lighting as per the standards should be provided in the parking lots and walkways leading to the buildings, and common areas like lift lobbies, corridors and stairwells. Proper training should be given to the management and maintenance staff (Daren Geoffrey Fisher, & Awais Piracha, 2012).

In the common areas security should patrol and residents should report the concerned staff when they notice any suspicious activity. To make common areas like outdoors play areas as safe locations. It should have natural surveillance. Vision from the windows, corridors and balconies should not be obstructed by placing drain pipes, parapets and ledges near to it. It affects natural surveillance of the roads; playground and children play areas. (Guidebook of crime prevention through environmental design, 2003)

Office/Retails/Hotels

The sight lines from the workstations of the receptionist to the entrance areas should be clear. The entrance to the washrooms should be highly visible. Adequate lighting should be provided in the back lines and loading/unloading areas.

Access to the loading/unloading areas should be lockable. All the shops that are closed lately should be clustered in one area and this cluster should be preferably formed at the entrance of the building. Providing public seating in the areas discourages loitering but promotes natural surveillance.

Proper signage should be provided for washrooms, telephones and other common areas. Unauthorized access should be restricted to the rooftops in any way. (Guidebook of crime prevention through environmental design, 2003).

Lighting at work. (2021, November 2). [Photograph]. Makegreatlight.

<https://www.makegreatlight.com/about-us/blog/block-fluorescent-lighting-work-one-way-not-to>

Parks/ Open Spaces and Public Toilets

They should be clearly visible from adjacent streets and shall be overlapped with residential and commercial areas. Trees, Bushes shall be made clear if they interfere with the sightlines or lighting, electronic systems such as cameras. Multiple entry exits shall be provided in parks. Activity generators such as cafes and restaurants, street food stalls should be encouraged. Activities should be located either along the edge of parks close to vehicular traffic facing the parks to avoid isolation some benches shall be placed and nowadays green gyms develop activities. Toilets should be near the children's playground.

Areas intended for low natural light in case of evening or night activities such as evening walks, tennis/badminton shall be highly visible, adequately lit and shall be away from isolated zones. Signs Information, maps and key plans including point of intersection of paths, entry, exits shall be clearly located at decision points or wherever possible with opening and closing hours of parks. Formal surveillance and cameras shall be installed and regular checked by attendants.

Park pathway. (n.d.). [Photograph]. 123RF.

https://www.123rf.com/photo_13635169_park-pathway.html

Underpasses/ Pedestrian overhead bridges/ Metro station/ Bus stands.

In an isolated area with low public volume, signs should be provided at strategic locations to indicate where it leads to and if any alternate route is available. High visibility and uniform lighting shall be provided. In case of sharp turns more than 60 degrees an angled full-length mirror should be placed to see along the corner. Activity generators shall be encouraged such as a small confectionery or cafes or street stalls that also creates improved visibility.

Lighted roadway. (n.d.). [Photograph]. Photostockeditor.
<https://photostockeditor.com/image/road-lighted-roadway-surrounded-with-buildings-street-90527>

Conclusion

For private spaces such as apartments, villas, bungalows, and other housing units, proper sightlines should be provided and those sightlines shall be wider and clear. Interaction with neighbours and having good communication could really avoid crime. In private spaces the windows, doors shall be glazed and not isolated from the property. Formal surveillance from neighbours, security guards could avoid most of the crimes. Electronic surveillance helps to figure out criminal acts sometimes possible to avoid the crime and if it happens it provides data for identification.

Environmental design at public spaces shall be done by providing adequate lighting wider spaces of approach, multi-level entry, and exit points. Regular maintenance of vegetation and other systems such as lighting, surveillance systems. Signage and information system shall be provided in all of the spaces, provide location maps at entry/exit points and provide floor plans at each level of the building, to help ease in escape in case of emergency/fire, fire routes and guided access for specially-abled.

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Funding

The author does not receive any financial support for the research, and publication of this article.

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Conscious Building and Infrastructure Designing: An Integrated approach to Prevent crime in building and neighbourhood - Sneha S.Reddy

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Abstract

Crime is a myriad of complex factors and a serious civic issue faced at buildings and neighborhood levels. As a result, Conscious Designing plays a vital role in reducing crime rate which will be proved through the paper. As per NCRB Records (statistics of 2020), the cognizable crime rate in India has increased by 28%. As per the record, burglary, robbery etc. cases have declined post COVID-19. To reduce the crime graph from here onwards becomes challenging post COVID. A recent appalling incident that took place in 2018 at Ayanavaram community, Chennai where a 12 year old girl has been rapped by blue collar workers and due to the sheer negligence. The paper focuses upon integrated and conscious planning strategies at both building and neighborhood level. To achieve these parameters, various research papers have been studied and the relevant and environmental design strategies that can be adopted passively have been explained in the paper under various principles of CPTED. The aim of the proposal is to make CPTED strategies mandatory by local authorities before project approvals.

Keywords: Conscious Designing, Natural surveillance and access control, Optimum landscaping and lighting, Maintenance, Activity control

Highlights/Relevance of Paper: The paper is appropriate for the present burning issue faced by India and an attempt has been put forward to contribute to the society through the content of the paper. To create a sustainable city, better quality of life, less fear personal safety and livelihood needs to be experienced. These parameters can be achieved only through conscious environmental designing process.

Introduction

Will there be a shining beacon of hope towards Crime Deterrence, Restitution and Reform aspects in India? As professionals, how can we contribute towards the crime rate reduction through environmental conscious designing? This paper sets to address the issue at building and neighborhood level by conscious environmental design strategies. Traditionally focus has been inclined more towards actions and punishments rather than crime prevention. Such a manmade hazard can be minimized through a quality design. “The proper design and effective use of the built environment can lead to a reduction in the fear and incidence of crime, and an improvement of the quality of life.” - CPTED, as defined by the National Crime Prevention Institute.

Conscious designing: Conscious design includes design awareness of long term and unplanned consequences of what we design and a continuous experimentation of our design process to build more sustainable products and services.

Crime

It is an act performed which causes harm to the society and creates panic in the society. It can be due to peer influence, poverty, lack of education and awareness, Heredity and brain activity

Natural surveillance

It is a concept where placement of physical features, people maximizes visibility i.e, unobstructed fenestrations etc., pedestrian friendly sidewalks, front porches, optimum nighttime lighting and lesser probability of committing crime.

Territoriality reinforcement

Territoriality is a design concept directed at reinforcing notions of proprietary concern and a “sense of ownership” in legitimate users of space thereby reducing opportunities for offending by discouraging illegitimate users. This concept includes features defining space divisions as per privacy using landscape pavements, designs, gateway treatments, signages, open fences etc.

Natural access control

It is a concept that denies crime targets. Physically people are guided through streets, sidewalks, building entrances, landscaping etc.

Maintenance and management

Proper maintenance prevents crime, which in return adds to the territorial reinforcement

Situational prevention: It seeks to reduce harm caused by crime through immediate situational modifications in the environment. For example: removal of target (parking a luxurious car in garage area rather than on street. Alert conscience by installing roadside signs to flash vehicle speed etc.

Activity control: It is a platform that accommodates passive and active leisure activities, wholesale night market, concerts, mobile stalls, food and drink businesses or restaurants in a community keeps the street alive and probability to check offenders. It creates a Defensible space. Activity Support can include any functions that enhance and promote interaction amongst the residents and any other legitimate users in the neighborhood (Worrall, 2008)

Figure 11 Factors affecting defensible space i.e, Natural surveillance, Building image, facilities juxtapositioning, space connectivity and territoriality. Source: (Al-Khafaji 2020)

Analysis

Problem/ study aspect	Research relevant Study	Results/findings
National Crime Records Bureau Statistics 2020	As per NCRB Crime statistics 2020, cognizable crime rate has increased by 28% with 14,45,127 in 2020 from 51,56,158 cases in 2019.Source: (NCRB 2021)	The statistics illustrates the crime rate in India .This becomes base for the research paper.

<p>Natural surveillance</p>	<p>Activity rooms such as kitchens, living/family rooms and lobbies to allow for good viewing of parking, streets or common areas. Managers, doormen, attendants and security personnel should have extensive views of these areas. Source: (D. n.d.)</p> <div data-bbox="450 483 1123 730" data-label="Image"> </div> <p>Figure 12 The glass lobby on left increases visibility and the tower on right ensure better lines of sight. Source: (Kruger 2005)</p> <div data-bbox="432 927 1123 1473" data-label="Image"> </div> <p>Figure 13 The openings cut into this wall allow views of the parking area. It increases natural light and allow sound to travel.</p>	<p>These examples explains how spaces in a building can act as a passive design for Natural surveillance.</p>
<p>Natural access control</p>	<p>Denial of access to target shall be achieved through creating design features include a highly visible gate ,placement of entrances and exits to be used by authorized persons or fencing to discourage unwanted access into private space or into dark or unmonitored</p>	<p>Natural access can be achieved through fencing, landscaping and space connectivity as per usage.</p>

	<p>areas, landscaping to control traffic flow. Source: (D. n.d.)</p> <p>Figure 14 Green belt for ease in access Source: (Kruger 2005)</p>	
<p>Territoriality reinforcement</p>	<p>Features of territoriality includes the use of low walls, defined entries, balconies and terraces, see-through screening , signage, landscape and paving patterns to clearly define the space around a unit entry as belonging to and the responsibility of the residents of the unit.</p> <p>Figure 15 Examples of people taking ownership of public space. Source: (Kruger 2005)</p>	<p>Territoriality reinforcement can be achieved through clear screening, signages, paving patterns</p>

	<p>Figure 16 Public and private zones defined with large windows, porches at building level and pavement treatments, street lighting and landscape designing at neighborhood level Source: (D. n.d.)</p>	
<p>Maintenance and management</p>	<p>Damaged fencing, overgrown hedges, litter and debris, broken windows as well as such factors as inattentive or overly-permissive management practices will attract likely offenders. Other side, the enhancement, maintenance and management of the built environment encourages the users of the area to respect their surroundings (e.g., removing graffiti and litter, avoiding overgrowth of hedge, fixing inoperative lighting, installing good locks, trimming trees, and exterior lighting at night and keep it all in working order).</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> </div> <p>Figure 17 Image ability of a place with and without maintenance</p>	<p>Dismantling damaged fencing, overgrown hedges, litter and debris to prevent offenders</p>

Figure 18 Above improving living conditions with medium density housing. Below Improving infrastructure i.e., roads for ease in access, comfort and proper sight lines

Figure 19 Improving infrastructure to make it pedestrian friendly and safe to access

Figure 20 Improving the quality of environment
(Source: Alexandra Renewal Project (ARP))

<p>Activity control/Night life activities in communities</p>	<p>Make an area appealing to appropriate pedestrian use: such as attractive landscaping, safety from car traffic and public art. Research studies found that well-used streets and bustling sidewalks were safer from violent crimes than deserted spaces. Source: (D. n.d.)</p>	<p>This explains the role of well maintained streets were safer from violent crimes. Night life activities</p>
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		acts as a defensible space (By Oscar Newman)
--	--	--

“DESIGN STRATEGIES” at Building and Neighborhood levels:

Natural surveillance:

Building level:

- Maximize full visibility of the property.
- Front door to be at least partially visible from street.
- ATM’s to face main road.
- Positioning of washrooms from reception areas.
- Encourage mixed use land developments designed with proper and unobstructed sight lines (Figure 11 and 12)

Figure 21 Surveillance through mixed use developments, uninterrupted sight lines and lighting for Natural surveillance. Source: (Plessis 2000)

Figure 22 Double glazing at front of properties allows natural surveillance
(Source: Safety and Security (Principles of Crime Prevention through 2014))

Neighborhood level:

- Avoid landscape blind spots.
- Locate play areas or recreational areas centrally visible from all blocks.
- Shrubs to be trimmed if more than 3 feet height and trees to 7 feet height.
- Allow shrubbery to be no more than 3 feet high for clear visibility in vulnerable areas.
- Unobstructed building entrance acts as natural surveillance (Figure 14,17)
- Proper fencing design promotes natural surveillance (Figure 15)
- Dwellings with fenestrations and balconies facing streets improve natural surveillance (Figure 18)
- Seating in active areas adds to natural surveillance (Figure 19)

Figure 23 Clear sight lines encourage natural surveillance (Left), Clear unobstructed building entrance (Right)

Figure 24 Fencing design promotes natural surveillance (left), After 1.2m height fencing open acts as a source for good sight lines (right)

(Source: Safety and Security (Principles of Crime Prevention through 2014)

Figure 25 Bridge instead of underpass (Left), Movement predictor well lit (Right)

Figure 26 Clear visibility at entrances

Figure 27 Dwellings addressing the street through fenestrations or balconies

Figure 28 Street number, size and positioning adds to maintenance of a space and management

Seating in active areas

Figure 29 Seating in active areas adds to natural surveillance

Figure 30 Oscar Newman sketch of wider corridor facing play area at River bend houses, New York for natural surveillance. Source: (Newman 1973)

Figure 31 Tilden houses, New York depicting surveillance of hallways from street

Windows have been inserted at the end of the corridor on each floor and at each landing of the fire stair. As a result the patrolling officer on the street can observe much of the activity in the public interior space of the building

Territoriality reinforcement:

Building level

Front porches acts as territory between street and home.

Neighborhood level

Define property lines with landscaping, fences. Street level differences from actual site, well lit street nameplate with minimum six inches height promotes territorial reinforcement.

- Pathways should be direct. All barriers along pathways should be permeable including landscaping, fencing etc. (Figure 22)
- Consider the installation of mirrors to allow users to see ahead and around corners.(Figure 25)
- The installation of glass or stainless steel panels in stairwells helps in territorial reinforcement. (Figure 26)

Figure 32 Permeable barrier and clear units identifications acts as territorial reinforcement.

Figure 33 Encourage free movement for pedestrians

Figure 34 Phone niche provision within car park acts as a safety measure (Left), Clear labels acts as territorial reinforcement at parking areas (Right)

Figure 35 Mirrors allow viewing around the corner of buildings

Figure 36 Glass panels used at stairwells promotes visibility (left), No seats outside toilets reduces loitering (Right)

(Source: Safety and Security (Principles of Crime Prevention through 2014)

Natural access control:

Building level

Balcony railings less than 42 inches height. Avoid opaque materials. Centrally locate vertical transportation services.

Neighborhood level

Install paving treatments, plantings, gateways.

Provide control access to areas on site (Figure 27)

Figure 37 Controlled access (Left), Clear sight lines (Right)

(Source: Safety and Security (Principles of Crime Prevention through 2014))

Figure 38 Columbus Houses, New York, an example of crime prone project where the elevator lobby is hidden from the view.

Maintenance and management:

- Removal of graffiti and encourages inclusive space. (Figure 29)
- Different parts of the development to be developed with a distinctive style. (Figure 30)

Figure 39 Removal of graffiti and encourages inclusive space.

Figure 40 Distinctive style for different parts of the development.

(Source: Safety and Security (Principles of Crime Prevention through 2014))

Situational prevention:

Situational prevention techniques can be achieved through improved street lighting, developed defensible spaces, property marking, signages etc. (Figure 31)

Increase the Effort	Increase the Risks	Reduce the Rewards	Reduce Provocations	Remove Excuses
Harden targets <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Steering column locks and immobilisers Anti-robbery screens Tamper-proof packaging 	Extend guardianship <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Take routine precautions: go out in group at night, leave signs of occupancy, carry phone "Cocoon" neighborhood watch 	Conceal targets <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Off-street parking Gender-neutral phone directories Unmarked bullion trucks 	Reduce frustrations and stress <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficient queues and polite service Expanded seating Soothing music/muted lights 	Set rules <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rental agreements Harassment codes Hotel registration
Control access to facilities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entry phones Electronic card access Baggage screening 	Assist natural surveillance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved street lighting Defensible space design Support whistleblowers 	Remove targets <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Removable car radio Women's refuges Pre-paid cards for pay phones 	Avoid disputes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Separate enclosures for rival soccer fans Reduce crowding in pubs Fixed cab fares 	Post instructions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> "No Parking" "Private Property" "Extinguish camp fires"
Screen exits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ticket needed for exit Export documents Electronic merchandise tags 	Reduce anonymity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Taxi driver IDs "How's my driving?" decals School uniforms 	Identify property <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Property marking Vehicle licensing and parts marking Cattle branding 	Reduce emotional arousal <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Controls on violent pornography Enforce good behavior on soccer field Prohibit racial slurs 	Alert conscience <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roadside speed display boards Signatures for customs declarations "Shoplifting is stealing"
Deflect offenders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Street closures Separate bathrooms for women Disperse pubs 	Utilize place managers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CCTV for double-deck buses Two clerks for convenience stores Reward vigilance 	Disrupt markets <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitor pawn shops Controls on classified ads License street vendors 	Neutralize peer pressure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> "Idiots drink and drive" "It's OK to say No" Disperse troublemakers at school 	Assist compliance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Easy library checkout Public lavatories Litter bins
Control tools/weapons <ul style="list-style-type: none"> "Smart" guns Disabling stolen cell phones Restrict spray paint sales to juveniles 	Strengthen formal surveillance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Red light cameras Burglar alarms Security guards 	Deny benefits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ink merchandise tags Graffiti cleaning Speed humps 	Discourage imitation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rapid repair of vandalism V-chips in TVs Censor details of modus operandi 	Control drugs and alcohol <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Breathalyzers in pubs Server intervention Alcohol-free events

Figure 41 Situational crime prevention techniques

Optimum landscaping and lighting:

As per Virginia CPTED Guidelines, at least 2 foot candles lighting level is to be maintained at parking and pedestrian levels. Also, use cut off fixtures with diffusers to focus lighting. Street lighting of minimum of 0.5 foot candles to be maintained.

- Shrubs and trees do not obstruct lighting.(Figure 32)
- Shrubs to be trimmed to 3 feet or below window sills.
- To deter unwanted entry plant thorny plants
- Avoid blank spaces.

Figure 42 Landscape and lighting design are not interfering with help of lighting islands.

Source: (Department n.d.)

- Use of solar street lighting reduces cost.
- Following BIS Standards for lighting to be made mandatory in India (Table 1,2)
- Appropriate street lighting to be maintained (Figure 33)
- Avoid light nuisance (Figure 35)
- Green space minimizes graffiti (Figure 36)

Type of Road	Road Characteristics	Average Level of Illumination on Road Surface in Lux	Ratio of Minimum/Average Illumination	Type of Luminaire Preferred
A-1	Important traffic routes carrying fast traffic	30	0.4	Cutoff
A-2	Main roads carrying mixed traffic like city main roads/streets, arterial roads, throughways	15	0.4	Cutoff
B-1	Secondary roads with considerable traffic like local traffic routes, shopping streets	8	0.3	Cutoff or semi-cutoff
B-2	Secondary roads with light traffic	4	0.3	Cutoff or semi-cutoff

Table 3 Recommended levels of illumination as per BIS,1981

Lamp		Application	Desired Illumination (Lux)	Mounting height (m)	Width of road (m)	Spacing between poles (m)	Uniformity ratio	Angle of tilt (degree)	Over hang (m)
Watt	Lamp output	Residential	6	6	8	30	0.24	5	0.8
70 w	5800 lumens	Shopping street/road	10	6	6	25	0.38	5	0.8
		Factory road	15	6	6	17	0.53	5	0.8
150 w	14000 lumens	Factory road							
250 w	27000 lumens		30	10	15	30	0.42	15	2.0

Table 4 Best practices for High Pressure Sodium Vapor

Source: (Energy Efficient Street lighting guidelines 2010)

Figure 43 Well lit pedestrian pathways (Left), Appropriate street lighting (Right)

Figure 44 Lighting and landscaping in maximizing lighting area

Figure 45 Avoid light nuisance

Figure 46 Green space minimizes graffiti

Natural lighting should be used where possible with consideration given to wall and ceiling materials to help reflect light.

- No entrapment spots should be included in any movement predictor.

Night life activities and activity control:

Building level:

- Encourage mixed use land developments designed with proper and unobstructed sight lines

Figure 47 Surveillance through mixed use developments, uninterrupted sight lines and lighting for Natural surveillance. Source: (Plessis 2000)

Figure 48 Night life activities with multifunctional spaces

Conclusion

Various design strategies have been proposed in terms of Natural surveillance, Territoriality reinforcement, Natural access control, Optimum lighting and landscaping, Maintenance and management, Situational prevention. These are adopted in various parts of the country and the research paper aims the readers to benefit with the environmental design strategies for the future buildings.

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Crime Control through Landscape Development of Neighbourhood Open Spaces - Sushama Parashar and Isha Rane

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Abstract

Neighbourhood open spaces include parks, gardens, parking lots, vacant plots, seating areas and playgrounds. Open spaces provide visual relief as well as recreational opportunities. People of all ages benefit from spending time outdoors and interacting with people. It benefits their physical as well as mental health. Apart from this, green open spaces have a positive effect on the microclimate of the neighbourhood.

Crime at neighbourhood level often takes place in deserted and neglected open spaces. There is a degree of insecurity and fear associated in the minds of people when visiting undeveloped and abandoned open spaces. Regular use of open spaces for community/ individual daily activities help maintain the space and leads to informal natural surveillance, deterring crime. Studies have established a significant association between green space maintenance and crime. Researcher Morgan Grove states that criminals look for spaces where they can operate without being seen or reported. They look for physical signs of neglect. Hence it is important to develop abandoned neighbourhood open spaces which are not only inviting but also become a secure and inclusive environment .

This paper focuses on controlling crime, using CPTED principles in the context of neighbourhood open spaces. The CPTED (Crime Protection Through Environmental Design) principles of maintenance, territoriality, natural access control and natural surveillance are important in landscape development. Location, access points, lighting, vegetation, activities for all ages, are instrumental in determining the frequency of the use of the space. Two case studies of open spaces, erstwhile used for some other purpose but became unkempt and hence abandoned are selected for the study. Landscape design interventions that elevate the users perception of safety have been introduced in these case studies. This development has improved the spatial and visual quality of these spaces and appraised their safety.

Keywords: *microclimate, abandoned, natural surveillance, maintenance, secure.*

Safe neighbourhood open spaces provide visual relief and recreation to the community. They bring people outdoors encouraging outdoor activities, making them the green lungs of the city. Effective use of unbuilt environment reduces the fear of crime and builds up the city life. People actively use these neighbourhood spaces creating constant visual surveillance. Hencelandsaped developed open spaces make cities safe and livable.

Introduction

There are a number of underdeveloped, neglected or abandoned open spaces present in many neighbourhoods of every city. They include vacant plots or plots which were erstwhile wastelands. People refrain from visiting or occupying such open spaces, fearing heinous activities like theft, abduction, attack or assault. Oftentimes, criminals specifically look for abandoned open spaces where they cannot be seen doing illicit activities. Hence there is a preconceived notion to refrain from visiting such neglected open spaces and not venture into them among residents. This leads to a conducive atmosphere for crime to thrive in the open space making the neighbourhood unsafe.

Developing such open spaces with CPTED (Crime Protection Through Environmental Design) principles in mind will help to tackle crime in the neighbourhood. The idea that environmental design can deter crime was first introduced by Jane Jacobs as 'Eyes on the Street', in her book 'Death and Life of American Cities ' (Jacobs, 1961; Jane's Walk Phoenix, 2009). The term CPTED was coined by Professor C. Ray Jeffery (Jeffery, 1971) and later expanded upon by Oscar Newman in his 'Defensible Space Theory' (Newman, 1976). The four main principles of CPTED are natural surveillance, natural access control, territorial reinforcement along with maintenance and management (Fox, 2021). Together they help make a space inviting, inclusive and safe for the people. Design of landscape elements like access points, gates, lighting, vegetation, signage and pathways are instrumental in determining the frequency of use of open space. This paper aims at exploring how different landscape elements and design considerations affect the perception of safety in a neighbourhood open space. It aims to study how CPTED principles can be applied to landscape design elements and design safer open spaces for crime control.

The city of Pune is witnessing the landscape development of a number of formal and informal open spaces. It interests one to study how these open spaces can be made safer leading to happier neighbourhoods and livable cities.

Aim, Objectives and Research Questions

Aim

To study neighbourhood landscape design interventions based on CPTED principles.

Objectives

1. To find out landscape design considerations that discourage crime in the neighbourhood and elevate the user's perception of safety .
2. To study redevelopment of abandoned open spaces for inclusive and safer neighbourhoods.

Research Questions

1. How can abandoned neighbourhood open spaces be developed so as to deter crime?
2. How can landscape development of open spaces make neighbourhoods safer?

Scope and Limitations

The research is limited to crime prevention and enhancement of safety through landscape design in neighbourhood open spaces. All electronic surveillance systems are not considered for this study.

Literature Review

Eyes on the Street

In her book 'Death and Life of American Cities ', Jane Jacobs wrote "There must be eyes on the street, eyes belonging to those we might call the natural proprietors of the street"(Jacobs, 1961; Jane's Walk Phoenix, 2009). Her theory suggests that having eyes on the street throughout the day will increase the safety of the neighbourhood by deterring criminal and nefarious activities. Researcher Morgan Grove states that criminals look for spaces where they can operate without being seen or reported (Grove, 2016). Hence informal surveillance will help discourage them to operate.

Broken Window Theory

The broken window theory by Wilson and Kelling (Kelling & Wilson, 1982) states that visible signs of neglect and abandonment increase the number of nefarious activities. Lack of

maintenance provides for an environment that deters civilians from using the open space frequently creating hiding spots for criminals and a conducive environment for nefarious activities. Regular maintenance, on the other hand, discourages criminal activity by sending a subconscious signal that the space and that it is under the resident's surveillance. Landscape development of open spaces thus helps in building a good image of the neighbourhood and increases the safety of the residents.

Defensible Spaces

The term 'Defensible Space' is coined by Oscar Newman in his 'Defensible Space Theory' (Newman, 1976). Defining territories and boundaries let people know that somebody is in charge, making it less likely to be used for criminal activities than an open space that is abandoned. Hence people start using it regularly, treating it as an extension of their homes, providing natural surveillance.

Methodology

The Case study method has been used for the research which included:

1. Observations
2. Non-structured Interviews

Crime at neighbourhood level often takes place in deserted and neglected open spaces. Studying neighbourhood open spaces that were erstwhile abandoned but later developed into landscaped parks helped in understanding the role landscaped development plays, in deterring crime. Two case studies in the city of Pune were identified for the above study.

The research is designed as a qualitative study. A qualitative approach allows the researchers to embed themselves in the research setting and understand from multiple perspectives, the setting and the phenomena. Observations helped the researchers to map what was happening in both cases. To investigate the reasons for the observations, non-structured interviews were carried out. A quantitative research would fall short of bringing forth the nuances of the cases.

Observations were carried out based on important aspects of landscape design, activities of users, and maintenance of the open space.

Following are the pointers used for carrying out the observations.

1. Vegetation : Type, Height, Location
2. Fencing :Material, height,
3. Lighting : Appropriate
4. Definition of hard and soft areas
5. Access points : Location, Number, Control, Visiting Hours
6. Neighbouring buildings : Typology, Proximity, Elevational Alterations
7. Signages
8. Facilities : Appropriate
9. Overall Maintenance
10. Activities of the users : Nature, time, duration

The recording the observations was as follows. The researchers visited the selected cases twice a day for two days. The visits were conducted at peak hour of 9 am and at 8pm when the crowd is waning. once on a weekday and a weekend. Various stakeholders interviewed were users, residents staying around the parks, maintenance and security staff and park administrators, following the interview guide, which brought forth a holistic understanding of the field.

Interview Guide:

1. Frequency and time of visit.
2. Safety quotient of lone users.
3. Identification of refuge dominant spaces.

As the interviews proceeded, unknown aspects relevant to the research were revealed by the respondents. The body language, expressions, activities and dialogue with the respondents gave an insight, adding value to the responses and observations recorded.

CASE STUDIES

Case 1: Lakaki Lake

The Lakaki Lake is located in Model Colony, an elite neighbourhood of Pune. The lake was an erstwhile an abandoned quarry, filled up with rain water, making it a breeding ground for mosquitoes and nefarious activities.

The landscape development of the lake was completed in 2001, designed and conceptualized architect Ravindra Bhan (Ravindra Bhan, n.d.).

Observations:

1. Vegetation : - Trees have tall trunks.
 - Shrubs are short. Ornamental shrubs are used.
 - Flowering plants and groundcovers are planted along the boundary.
2. Fencing : - Low decorative fencing around the lake.
 - High chain link fences along the boundary.
3. Lighting : -No light poles along the pathway, so as to not disturb the birds.
 - Light poles along the surrounding lanes provide sufficient light and reinforce the boundaries of the development.
4. Definition of hard and soft areas : - Paved pathway along the lake.
5. Access Points : - Single entry point with security guard
 - Open during the day.
6. Neighbouring buildings : - Apartment buildings and bungalows
7. Signages : - Denoting entrance
8. Facilities : -Toilets and Seating along pathways, gazebos
9. Overall Maintenance : -Seating, toilets and landscaping is well maintained.
10. Activities of the users : -Jogging, morning and evening walks
 - Peak hours are at sunrise and sunset
 - Average duration of visit is half an hour
11. Other Observations : - The park felt safer because it was surrounded by

Fig. 49. Observations at Lakaki Lake

Source: Generated by authors, 2021

Non-Structured Interview Responses

1. Frequency and time of visit : Majority of respondents recorded daily visits either in the morning or evening.
2. Safety quotient of lone users : Since most of the neighbouring buildings overlook the lake, users feel their cry for help will be heard and responded to. Hence they feel safe venturing alone in the park.
3. Identification of refuge dominant spaces : Patches that had high cliffs or compound walls obstructing visual permeability at eye level were perceived as unsafe as they can be refuge dominant spaces.
4. Other Responses : Microclimate, quality of water, biodiversity in the neighbourhood has improved. Connection of people

Case 2 : Hirwai Jogging Track

The Hirwai track runs perpendicular to three major roads of Pune: Prabhat Road, Bhandarkar Road and BMCC Road. The track was erstwhile a dried up canal. Uncontrolled growth of vegetation, absence of maintenance and lighting made the space inaccessible. Lack of clear territorial reinforcement and defined access points made the open space vulnerable to crime. The construction of the Hirwai track was completed in 2004. It is designed by architect Shobha Bopatkar (Hindustan Times, 2019).

1. Vegetation : - Trees have thin and tall trunks.
 - Shrubs are short.
2. Fencing : - Majority of plots along the path have chain link fence.
 - Some plots have opaque fencing.
 - Division between walking and cycle track with chain link fencing in some patches.
3. Lighting : - Light poles at regular intervals along the pathway.
4. Definition of hard and soft areas : - Walking Track has mud path
 - Cycling track is paved.
5. Access Points: - Guarded access points only at road junctions
 - Walking track.
 - Cycle track open 24x7
6. Neighbouring buildings : - Apartment buildings and bungalows along both edges lengthwise.
7. Signages : - Denoting entrance, dustbins and toilets
8. Facilities : - Toilets, seating, games, gazebos, children's play areas, outdoor gym
9. Overall Maintenance : - Seating, toilets, landscaping and other facilities are well maintained.
10. Activities of the users : - Jogging, morning and evening walks
 - Peak hours are at sunrise and sunset
 - Average duration of visit is an hour
 - Cyclists of all ages use the track throughout the day
11. Other observations : - Cycle track provides a connection between the main roads.

- A number of luxury apartment buildings have mushroomed along the edges of the track.

Fig. 2.Observations at Hirwai Jogging Track

Source: Generated by authors, 2021

1. Frequency and time of visit : Majority of respondents recorded daily visits either in the morning or evening after working hours.
2. Safety quotient of lone users : Senior Citizens and children feel safe using the track alone even during dark hours as they are able to see the people in windows or balconies of neighbouring buildings.
3. Identification of refuge dominant spaces : Patches which had high cliffs or compound walls obstructing visual permeability at eye level were perceived as unsafe as they can be refuge dominant spaces. Patches with bamboo grass used as separation between the track and seating area was perceived unsafe.

SENIOR CITIZENS AND CHILDREN
USING THE TRACK IN THE EVENING

FENCING WITH CLIMBERS AND BOUNDARIES DEFINED BY
BAMBOO GRASS CREATING REFUGE DOMINANT SPACES

Fig. 3. Observations at Hirwai Jogging Track

Discussion

A visual connection was observed between the residents of the neighbouring buildings and the open space in both the case studies due to trees which have thin trunks, tall height and low height bushes. They allowed for natural surveillance. As in case of the Lakaki Lake, dense but low height bushes naturally controlled access into the lake. Along some patches of the Hirwai Jogging Track, tall bamboo grass used for defining boundaries had a negative effect on the visual permeability. It aided for creation of refuge dominant spots that may be used for nefarious activities. Similarly, uncontrolled growth of vegetation resulting in inaccessible or blind spots creates an environment favoured by criminals.

Fig. 4.Vegetation and Visual Permeability

Source: Generated by authors, 2021

When people from neighbouring houses are able to directly see the opposite boundary of the open space, they are able to keep a watch on the activities happening along the whole expanse of that open space. When users are venturing into an open space, they feel in control if its boundaries are visible. Women tend to occupy locations in parks from where they have better visual control over the exit points (Natu, 2018) In case of a circular or squarish plot, it is essential for the connection to be maintained from all sides, along the diagonal or diameter. However, in case of linear open spaces, it is enough if visual connection is achieved either along the length or the width.

As in case of the Hirwai Jogging track, though the pathway is winding and does not have visual connection along the length, the thorough visibility along the short width helps in crime control. Fencing was observed to be instrumental in maintaining ideal visual connection. Chain link fencing provided for thorough visibility. However, opaque covering or climbers on such fences obstruct visual permeability. Edges which were opaque and high, especially along some patches of the Hirwai Jogging Track which has short width, made users feel unsafe.

Fig. 5. Visual Surveillance in Open Spaces

Source: Generated by authors, 2021

A large number of people were seen occupying both the parks selected as case studies. According to the users, they felt safe because of the number of people around them. People visited the open space on a regular basis because it had a defined purpose. Paving, fencing, adequate lighting and signages helped them to identify the purpose of the open space. Community formation takes place due to increased interaction between people, further intensifying the feeling of ownership and maintenance of the open spaces and the cycle continues to make the neighbourhoods safer, thus explaining the increasing rate of new luxury housing constructions.

HIRWAI JOGGING AND CYCLING TRACK

LAKAKI LAKE

Fig. 6. Activity generators, paving and ground covers defining use

Source: Generated by authors, 2021

Findings

Based on the above discussions, following are the landscape design considerations for crime control in neighbourhood open spaces.

Natural Surveillance

1. High level canopy trees ensuring visual permeability.
2. Avoid refuge dominant spaces in landscaping.
3. Linear open spaces should have thorough visual connectivity along the width while circular or squarish open spaces should have visual connectivity throughout the diameter or diagonal of the space.

Natural access control

1. Low height hedges.
2. Paving materials and ground covers defining use.
3. High Fencing using barbed wire enabling visual permeability.

Territorial Reinforcement

1. Clearly defining hard and soft areas.
2. Signages defining use of open space.
3. Appropriate lighting (lamp posts and bollards).

Maintenance and Management

1. Legible Signages.
2. Well maintained facilities.
3. Well maintained landscape.

Conclusion

Crime at neighbourhood level often takes place in deserted and neglected open spaces. The landscape design and development of such open spaces with the help of CPTED principles helps in reducing crime rate and making the neighbourhood safe. Controlling crime is essential to make neighbourhoods livable, safe and inclusive, ensuring people of all ages have access to green open spaces. Effective use of wastelands reduces the fear of crime and builds up the city life. Hence landscape development open spaces make cities safe and livable.

Developing a neglected neighbourhood open space leads to an increase in people coming outdoors and using the open space. People actively use these neighbourhood spaces creating constant visual surveillance. Natural access control and territorial reinforcement discourages trespassing and vandalism, leading to cleaner, maintained and aesthetically pleasing landscaped areas. The open spaces become inviting and inclusive as senior citizens, children and women begin feeling safer while occupying them. Safer neighbourhoods bring people outdoors encouraging outdoor activities, making them the green lungs of the city. The image of the neighbourhood is uplifted. As a result, there is an increase in property rates of the neighbourhood.

Acknowledgments

The authors are thankful to the interview respondents and to Dr. A. S. Natu for his invaluable guidance.

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Evaluation of CPTED Principles & Scope of Enhancement at Neighbourhood Level: A Case Study of Kolar Road, Bhopal, M.P. – Aakritee Arya and Akshat Saxena

Aim

The aim of the study is to evaluate the existing condition of the delineated area and to provide required design interventions to enhance security measures.

Objectives

- To study the various types of crimes and identify the locations of occurrence of these crimes.
- To conduct the CPTED specific audits and survey at identified locations with the help of extensive literature study.
- To evaluate the existing conditions and provide required design based solutions to prevent criminal activities.

The study targets the public, semi-public and physical infrastructure at neighborhood level

- Identifying the locations
 - Consultation with a closed group
 - Public & Semi-public Zones
- Visual Survey
 - Identification of design problems with respect to CPTED Principles.
- Corroboration through Interviews
 - Discussion with at least 10 residents around the selected locations.
- Suggesting possible solutions
 - Design solutions on the basis of 5 CPTED Principles.
 - Infrastructure provisions

	Swarn Jayanti Park	Mahabalipur Bus Stop	Road Stretch A	Road Stretch B
Existing Building/ Infra Condition	Blue	Yellow	Blue	Yellow
Street Lighting	Red	Green	Purple	Red
Visual Barriers	Red	Red	Green	Green

Table 1 - Parameters Of Analysis Of Identified Locations

Identification of Typology of crimes occurring at study locations

Association of criminal activities with the identified locations on the basis of following factors-

- Consultation with Local residents.
- Consultation with Kolar Road Police station.
- NCRB & SCRB Data 2015-21.

Consultation Groups

- Students (School & College)
- 23 participants
 - Age group 15-20
 - Students with own vehicles
 - Pedestrians
 - 8 male & 15 female participants
- Office and Commercial workers
- 34 Participants
 - Shopkeepers & shop workers
 - Own vehicle, pedestrian & public transport
 - Age group- 18-50
- Local Residents
- 28 participants
 - Families of 4-6 members esp. housewives
 - Houses adjacent to identified locations.
- Senior Citizens
- 8 Participants
 - Age 55 and above
 - Frequently use public spaces like park and street shops.
 - Mostly pedestrian

Location 1: SWARN JAYANTI PARK

Photo taken at 6:40 pm at the gate of the park

Road in front of the park clearly shows non functioning street light

Criminal Activities	Vandalism, Eve teasing, mugging, Sexual Assault, physical assault
Site Issues	No physical surveillance by guards, Poor maintenance of street lights, trees along the fence create visual barrier, poor maintenance inside the park.
Strategies Applied	Natural Surveillance, maintenance, Access control
Suggested Interventions	Eliminate the continuous line of trees along the fence, encourage site movement by interactive social events, infrastructure maintenance, street mall.

Location 2: MAHABALIPUR BUS STOP

Parking space b/w bus stop & shop

Criminal Activities	Vandalism, Drug abuse, mugging, Sexual Assault, physical assault
Site Issues	Formation of an enclosed negative space(parking in daytime) between the bus stand and the newly constructed shop behind enclosed from 3 sides, no enclose or fencing in front of bus stop leads to illegal parking
Strategies Applied	maintenance, Access control, visual control
Suggested Interventions	Eliminate the panels at the back of the bus stop to maximize visibility from road side, Controlled parking at the rear of the stop, Physical barrier through plantation/ fencing in front of the stop to channel only the bus movement, Interactive space through graffiti & murals.

Road Stretch A (From D-Mart to Tulip Greens) & Road Stretch B (Sagar Green Hills towards Kaliyasot Dam)

Criminal Activities	Vandalism, Eve teasing, mugging, Sexual Assault, physical assault, Substance abuse, threat from wildlife
Site Issues	Poor maintenance of street lights, Abandoned properties, unprotected constructed sites, valley along the road
Strategies Applied	maintenance, Access control, territorial reinforcement
Suggested Interventions	Street activities like vendors, road maintenance, fencing along the valley side, police checkpoints at regular intervals, walkways, signage, streetscaping, landscape pockets.

A Landscape-based approach to ensure a safe environment using CPTED : Neighborhood Level Security/City Level Security using CPTED Principles - Ar. Shivani Paliwal, Prof. Dr. Saleem Akhtar

SOA – RGPV Bhopal

Aim

The paper aims to give recommendations of landscape based approaches for the professionals under the Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design.

Objective

Understanding the basic concepts of CPTED, its relevance and importance.

Classifying the landscape based approaches of CPTED to give recommendations.

Methodology

Secondary study was adopted as method to conduct this research. Several researches were analyzed to understand the idea of CPTED. The researches were chosen on two grounds, first – it explained the concepts of CPTED both first and second generations and secondly it dealt with the applications in outdoor environment at neighborhood scale.

The occurrence of violence and crime is tried to be reduced by applying CPTED principles in an area by creating *positive interactions* or *congregations* with corresponding planning of the built environment in the surrounding

CPTED PRINCIPLES

- Natural Surveillance – *ensure that the environment is well maintained so that it could keep the safer surrounding*
- Natural Access Control – *vegetation design such as fence, flower bed, hedges, planting bed*
- Territorial Reinforcement – *segregation between public and private spaces*
- Maintenance – *park has to be maintained as to avoid criminal behaviour*

DEVELOPMENT COMPONENT OF CPTED:

- *Layout Design*
- *Access and Pedestrian Walkways*
- *Soft landscaping and urban design element*
- *Car parks*
- *Lighting*
- *Security devices*

Management and Maintenance

Jane Jacob gave her three points forming the foundation of CPTED, which says

- *A city street must have a clear demarcation between public and private space, what later became known as hierarchy of space – territorial reinforcement*
- *There must be eyes on the street – natural surveillance, and*

- *Areas need to be well used with good land use diversity, what later evolved into more advanced CPTED planning strategies*

As per the famous book called *Defensible Spaces* by Oscar Newman the basic strategies of CPTED have been named as First Generation CPTED, these four strategies are:

- *Territorial reinforcement*
- *Natural surveillance*
- *Access control*
- *Image (management and maintenance)*

Though these strategies were well received but there were more advanced strategies made in First Generation CPTED and still continue to evolve like:

- *Movement predictors*
- *Displacement controls*
- *Deflecting offenders*
- *Compatible land uses*
- *Boundary effects*

The Second Generation CPTED theory professes that only territoriality can not prevent the criminal events but a sense of neighbourliness is felt mutually by residents of the particular area. Hence came the Second Generation CPTED in place which has four 'C' strategy:

- *Social Cohesion*
- *Connectivity*
- *Community Culture*
- *Threshold Capacity*

Surveillance is when people in their homes can observe the coming and going in the street and the people in the street can observe the homes and front gardens

LANDSCAPE BASED INTERVENTIONS:

From the aforementioned points the principles were identified which are enlisted along with their objective and ways or methods in which they could be achieved. Those principles are - natural surveillance, natural access control, territoriality, program support, vegetation and fear of crime, safety design principle, short term planning of crime prevention, long-term planning of crime prevention.

S No.	PRINCIPLE	OBJECTIVE	INTERVENTION
1.	Natural Surveillance	Increase the visibility of a property or building	Appropriate landscaping through defined pathways, street lights, windows etc.
		Maximizing the potential to deter crime by making the offender's behaviour easily noticeable	
2.	Natural Access Control	Guides people entering and leaving a space	Appropriate placement of entrances, exits, fences, landscaping, and lighting
		Separating public property from private property, making the person look conspicuous while entering a place where he should not be going	Using a thorny shrub can discourage someone from entering a private area
		OBJECTIVE	INTERVENTION

	<p>Sphere of territorial influence that can be perceived by, and may deter, potential offenders</p>	<p>Defined property lines and clear distinctions between private and public spaces can be created using landscaping, pavement designs, decorative gateways, signs, and fences.</p>
	<p>Note: Broken Windows Theory" by Wilson and Kelling says that if property is not kept up, or looking like someone cares about the property, it is soon vandalized</p>	
	<p>Using personal to keep an eye on areas that have the potential to be crime problems also called activity support</p>	<p>Creating a nice smoking area that has a full view of the parking area aids the smoking staff watching the parking area like free security, a win - win situation</p>
	<p>To reduce places that offer prospect and refuge as these places are that a potential offender would favour</p>	<p>Creating multiple visible escape routes defined through manicured vegetation</p>
	<p>Providing good visibility around the open spaces</p>	<p>Good pedestrian linkages and walkways, and reducing 'blind spot' of potential criminal behaviour by configuring the vegetation design</p>

		Decreasing crime for short term	Lighting or illuminate a target area such as roadsides, public recreational areas
			Controlling the vegetation design
		Adopting long term solutions for crime prevention	Maintenance of landscape and prevent the routes and develop clear space
			Increase exposure and parking area
			Maintenance and management of landscapes

Places prioritized for active public or private intervention where landscape-based interventions could be made may include

- Multi-unit residential developments
- Street Malls

- Entertainment centres
- Tourist areas
- Civic centres and plazas
- Public parks and playgrounds
- Pedestrian bridges and overpasses
- Public transport stations and stops
- Pedestrian and cycle routes
- Car parks
- Public toilets
- Bank teller machines

The development component in parks and other public open spaces

- Lighting
- Signage
- Visibility

Conclusion

The landscape-based intervention that we see in the above sections are intended to create a secure environment in less obvious manner where it does not depend on mechanical or electrical equipment which might be vandalised or can get broken. Obvious measures might detract from the aesthetics of a site and adversely draw attention to their implementation. It tries to bring aesthetical solutions to site which involves people in a manner where they indulge in more social ways and the sense of neighbourliness and ownership increases vigilance and creates a sense of safety amongst the users.

The paper has summarised such interventions that can be directly verified in an already existing design of open space where modifications could be proposed based on this list. These measures could be taken up as recommendations in creating new spaces by both Landscape Professional and urban designers.

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Building safer communities through environmental design - at an urban community level - Ar. Harshita Vangara, Dr. K.S. Ananth Krishna

Introduction

A safe community is one in which people can live, work, and play in a secure and healthy environment. The environment can have a big impact on people's perceptions of safety. Even in low-crime areas, certain settings can instill a sense of safety and security while others can instill a sense of fear. In this regard, planning and design measures can be utilized very successfully to enhance feelings of safety in areas where people feel vulnerable. The right design and effective use of the built environment can contribute to a decrease in crime, fear and an increase in overall quality of life. The idea that the physical environment might boost or decrease criminal chances is not new. It has been intensively investigated internationally over a number of decades. There is widespread agreement that certain sorts of crimes can be reduced if the environment is properly planned, developed, and maintained. Environmental design has formed an integral part of many crime prevention initiatives in countries such as the UK, USA, Canada, The Netherlands and Australia.

Key issues:

- Lack of safety in our living.
- Increasing crime rate in the urban communities.
- Crime issues like – Robbery/theft, Sexual assault, Drugs, Kidnaps etc. growing rapidly in urban communities.

Aim & objectives of the study:

The objective is to review appropriate planning and design principles in the built environment to reduce the causes of and chances for criminal events. The research will address the fear of crime in the built environment in order to create a safe community

Crime:

In a social and legal context, crime refers to a combination of facts or assumptions (causes, effects, and goals) that are part of a case in which criminal acts were done, and the application of which is determined by the agent of a sentence or security measure criminal.

Prevention of crime:

The endeavor to lessen victims and deter crime and criminals is known as crime prevention. It refers to government efforts to reduce crime, enforce the law, and preserve the criminal justice system.

Environmental design for crime prevention:

The right design and effective use of the built environment may lead to a reduction in the fear and incidence of crime, as well as an enhancement in the quality of life.

Small intimate park with effective surveillance from adjacent sites

Small intimate park idea extended to form a network of effectively surveilled parks

Correct

Route layout facilitates pedestrian movement

Wrong

Pedestrians take shortcuts over private land

Route layout discourages pedestrian movement

QUALITY OF ENVIRONMENT

Role of planning and design professionals:

When aligning local government functions with crime prevention objectives, officials involved with urban design, town planning, and architecture could be responsible for a number of activities.

These include:

- Developing and implementing design and urban planning guidelines aimed at reducing crime.
- Designing retrospective improvements to physical environments in support of crime prevention.
- Promoting performance zoning in support of crime prevention and applying a flexible approach to zoning standards, for example reducing large areas of vacant land by identifying appropriate land uses.
- Ensuring context-specific design and management of the built environment to reduce crime;
- Contributing to the planning and implementation of integrated crime prevention strategies, especially with regards to aspects related to the physical environment; and

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People's perception of safety on street and its relation to the immediate built environment: A construct based in Indian communities and street design in the light of CPTED strategies –
Dr. Parama Mitra and Prof. (Dr) Suchandra Bardhan

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Abstract

The sense of safety and crime is a complex phenomenon that involves a mix of several attributes. The feeling of safety is linked to the built elements that make an urban neighbourhood. Safety in urban space is a vast domain, wherein people's preference can be studied.

The current study is done to identify this connect between the urban design elements present in Urban streets and roads in India and the feeling of safety by the users. For this study, a popular approach to urban planning to prevent crime and mitigate the fear of crime by improving the physical surroundings of the neighborhood CPTED (crime prevention through environmental design) is considered to identify the observable parameters.

This paper thus investigates the effects of CPTED measures on fear of crime by analyzing behavioral data of residents as well as the passers-by in the selected site. Survey data from 5 different streets in the 2-tier city, Bhopal is done. This data is collected through a designed questionnaire and an observation template. These questionnaires and the observation-checklist template is based on CPTED approaches. The analysis shows the two different perceptions: People's perception and the designer's conception of a safe street (based on CPTED parameters). This is scored in a scale and the trend studied. Thus, the relation of urban design parameters to user's perception is discernible and gives a direction to think about the contextuality of this approach.

This study tries to relate the concept that "sense of safety" is very much dependent on the users and any decision in built form without the actual users may not fulfill the real objective.

Keywords: *Sense of safety, CPTED, people's perception, physical design parameters, urban street design.*

Highlights/Relevance of Paper:

Considering the issue that safety is a basic need, physical environment design for of urban areas requires design approach that can be linked to that of safety. Oscar Newman's "Defensible Space" first paved its way for the concept of CPTED, an approach which can be defined as technique for reducing the rate of crime in an urban area by environmental design approach. This study checks if - ***design and use of the built environment based on CPTED norms can***

improve the quality of life through crime prevention and reduce the fear of crime, therefore, provide a feeling of safety in the community in Indian context.

Introduction

We know that starting from the dawn of civilization, mankind has regarded safety as a basic need, and it is at the 2nd tier of Abraham Maslow's "hierarchy of needs" pyramid. Urban safety is that which "...are referring not only to criminal behaviour, but to a number of factors that make the urban environment unsafe; these range from the real risk, to fear and uneasiness." (Directorate-General Justice, 2007).

India is the 7th largest country in the world and the largest in South-East Asia. Presently having a population of estimated 1.37 billion it anchors the 2nd position in the world, just after China (NIC, 2021). With its teeming urban problems, the issue which is bothering the entire nation is that of staggering crime rates and growing safety issues in urban areas.

Taking into account this issue, physical environment design for urban areas require design approach that can be linked to that of safety. Oscar Newman's "Defensible Space" (Newman, 1972) first paved its way for the concept of CPTED, (Crime Prevention through environmental Design) which is one approach which can be defined as technique for reducing the rate of crime in an urban area by environmental design approach. The main premises with which the concept of CPTED developed first under Newman, then the 2nd generation CPTED by Saville and Cleveland, 1998 is that the physical environment plays an important role in the occurrence or absence of crime. The initial hypothesis constructed for this study is that the correct design and use of the built environment based on CPTED norms can improve the quality of life through crime prevention and reduce the fear of crime, therefore, provide a feeling of safety in the community.

What CPTED does not mention is the context of the place or demography of the people belonging. The modified hypothesis is, "feeling of safety" is very much dependent on the users and any decision in built form without the actual users may not fulfill the real objective.

Aim of the study

A survey was conducted to understand how the built environment can affect the psychology of people walking on the streets. The purpose of this survey is to document the crime and safety challenges on the selected zone and investigate if user's perception tallies with the designers' perception.

Objective of the study

The specific objective is to investigate the physical design parameters that can affect people's perception of safety on a street and promote feeling of the same.

The research questions on which the study focuses are:

1. What is the safety expectation rating of streets based on urban design parameters (according to CPTED)? Safety expectation rating here is used to express personal feeling of safety in numerical terms as in Likart scale.
2. What is user's perception of safety on those streets in Indian context/ setting?
3. To investigate if they are in concordance with each other.

Limitations

A set of safety assessment criteria was derived from the CPTED checklist, (the parameters used in this research is detailed in section 3.2) and the visual and perceptual survey was conducted. The site selected for the research includes five streets in the central part of city of Bhopal, India, the choice rationale of which is discussed in detail in the section 4.

The main aim of this research being the user's perception on the feeling of safety, the survey was conducted among the pedestrians using those streets during the survey period. The total number of pedestrian (user) sample thus was 125, an average of 25 samples per street under study. Majority of the study subjects considered were during the daytime as compared to the nighttime, hence night –time perception is not considered. The main parameters have been rated based on the overall perception on the sub-parameters.

Conceptual Constructs Used in this Study

To conduct this study, the basic premises of CPTED was studied and the salient parameters were selected to form the basic framework of the survey questionnaire.

“CPTED was originally coined and formulated by criminologist C. Ray Jeffery. A more limited approach, termed defensible space, was developed concurrently by architect Oscar Newman. Both men built on the previous work of Elizabeth Wood, Jane Jacobs and Schlomo Angel.

Jeffery's book, 'Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design' came out in 1971, but his work was ignored throughout the 1970s" (Jusiewicz, 2011). Newman's book, "Defensible Space: - Crime Prevention through Urban Design" came out in 1972. (What is CPTED, 2017) The parameters thus selected are as follows: territoriality, natural surveillance, maintenance, access control, and the hierarchy of spaces.

The first 4 definitions are enlisted as below from the article “Crime Prevention through Environmental Design” by [Mollie Krehnke](#) (Krehnke, 2013) (CPTED(A), 2018).

- **“Natural Access Control:** Design features that clearly indicate public routes and discourage access to private structural elements. These features decrease an opportunity for crime by creating in an offender a perception of unacceptable risk when attempting access to private areas, which marks the stranger as a possible

intruder. Such design features include placement of entrances and exits, fencing, and landscaping to control traffic flow”.

- **“Natural Surveillance:** Design features that increase the visibility of a property. These features maximize the ability of persons in the area to see persons in the vicinity and avoid trouble and allow external activities to be seen from adjacent building structures by persons who could call for help. Such design features include landscaping, lighting, window and stairway placement, and building entrance and garage layouts”.
- **“Territorial Reinforcement:** Design features that clearly indicate public and private structural elements of a property. An individual will develop a sense of territoriality for a space with frequent activities in an area, a sense of ownership. With this feeling of ownership, the individual will "want" to defend his environment. This ownership does not necessarily mean legal ownership; it maybe a perceived ownership, such as the sense of ownership that employees feel for the office in which they work. The sense of territory and ownership by an individual is reinforced through regularly scheduled activities, inspections, and maintenance”.
- **“Maintenance:** Characteristics of an environment that express ownership of the property. Deterioration of a property indicates less ownership involvement which can result in more vandalism, also known as the Broken Window Theory. If a window is broken and remains unfixed for a length of time, vandals will break more windows. Crime is more prevalent in areas that are not maintained; as a result law-abiding persons do not feel safe and do not want to frequent those areas”. (CPTED(B), 2018)
- **“Hierarchy of spaces:** As a direct offshoot from territoriality, this concept can be derived. Oscar Newman in his book of “defensible space” (1972) has divided the space into Public, semi-public, semi-private, and private”. (CPTED, 2017)

Survey Methodology

Data Collection

CPTED safety audit checklist has several physical design parameters. Also, it has a set of parameters where it requires the users to check if the designs (for each parameter) are “satisfactory” or “un-satisfactory”. This is a binary opinion. However, the ‘safety feeling’ also rely on people’s perception and may vary from person to person thus a range of data is required to express their opinion.

Step 1 - A survey questionnaire is created for study using parameters from CPTED. The survey has two parts, some qualitative and some quantitative, so that an overall understanding can be derived from both the subjective parameters (feeling of safety) and objective parameters that

refer to the understanding of presence or absence of these design features. The measures for assessing against each parameter are listed.

Step 2 - After constructing survey form based on design parameters, a survey based on interviews with the study subjects and visual observation was conducted on weekday during the daytime.

User's perception mapping was done by random sample selection, from the samples from the study sites. The people present on the study stretches were randomly interviewed about their attitude towards crime and experiences using CPTED scale and physical design features. The data entered through a scale of 5, where 1 denoted least value and 5 denoted highest value and 3 is average score.

Step 3 - The highest number of occurrences of the value (central tendency) was calculated by finding the mode for each parameter on each survey zone. Observations were recorded on maps as per the Observation Template.

Comparison of each safety criteria is observed, based on the two parallel data, and the trend is plotted for each zone. Thus, the similarities and differences in the trend are identified and anomaly is observed between designed built features (based on safer environment standards) and user's perception of a safe environment.

The process is explained in Chart 1 given below.

Chart 50. Methodology of Study

Source: Generated by authors, 2021

Research Parameters

Parameters for direct observation and survey questionnaire are obtained from the CPTED strategies and from understanding the usability - nature of Indian streets. The questionnaire was targeted to Indian population who have resided in the study area, thus some screening questions were set to get the ideal set.

Only those data are used which conform to the acceptable set.

The examples of the nature of questions included in the survey are following: -

1. Socioeconomic status- gender, age, residence (permanent, temporary)
2. Walking frequency
3. Territoriality (abandoned buildings nearby)
4. Surveillance (CCTV, guards/police, building frontage, window openings/ balconies, people in shops)

5. Lighting (adequate, ambient)
6. Murals (identifiable or objectionable graffiti)
7. Road design (width of the road, sidewalk, street furniture)
8. Type of activity (land use- specifically commercial- residential mixed areas)

Study Area: Streets Near “Nutan College”, Southern Bhopal

The area lies within a busy residential patch, southern part of the city Bhopal, capital of Madhya Pradesh state in India. It occupies approximately a central location in the vast Indian Territory.

The chosen city is a two-tier city (in the anvil of Smart City Missions) having some smart goals as per the Mission statement. The core infrastructure elements in the “Smart Cities: Mission statements and Guidelines” issued by GOI, Ministry of Urban Development, June 2015 include 10 pointers of which one is, “safety and security of citizens, particularly women, children and the elderly”. (*Annexure 4: Challenge Stage 2: Criteria and Indicative Table of Contents, 4.1 Criteria, article 6*). (Ministry of Housing & Urban Affairs, GoI, 2017).

The project, “Mobile based Safety Audits to collect data on Women Safety” was undertaken by ‘Safetipin’ with UN Women in many Indian cities including Bhopal. The safety audits were conducted by the volunteers from Sangini Gender Resource Centre and WRI India.

Based on the report of ‘Safetipin’ on assessing the safety zones and unsafe zones in Bhopal, a particular area of around Nutan College has been selected comprising of five roads for the present study. These roads have safety score varying from 2 to 4 out of a total of 5, thus offering varied conditions to apply the study methodology.

Fig. 51. Map of Bhopal District showing the City of Bhopal

Source: Public Works Dept, Bhopal

Fig. 2. Map of Study Area

Source: Public Works Dept, Bhopal

Classification of Survey Streets

The study area, with the identified streets having different characteristics, is as discussed below.

Street 1: This Street (coloured orange in Figure 3) has Institutional, commercial as well as government residences, the majority being the commercial activity zone.

Street 2: As we walked down this Street (coloured yellow in Figure 3), it was found to have abandoned buildings and spaces. It was also not well lit and had no good surveillance.

Street 3: The reason for considering it was because this Street (coloured blue in Figure 3) was one of the Main roads of Bhopal and had a very good road design as compared to the rest of the considered streets.

Street 4: This was the street (coloured green in Figure 3) where the main road ended and the commercial area began which hence had different characteristics from the main road.

Street 5: This Street (coloured red in Figure 3) is completely different from the rest of the zones as it had no lights at all and was completely covered with a row of trees along the street. There was no sign of surveillance, be it passive or active.

Fig. 3. Map of Study Area , Source: Author.

Fig. 4. Map showing the five selected streets and their visual characteristics

Source: Author

Data Collection

The survey is conducted in each street; the people's perception is recorded in a 5-point Likert scale for each study parameter that was identified. A Modal value of the data is calculated to identify the maximum occurrence of a particular score for one parameter and thus a majority score is deduced for each parameter for that particular street. The scoring was also done by the surveyor based on the observation made on the Observation template (Table 1) generated through CPTED guidelines.

Site Survey

Visual survey observational template: The following template (Table 1) is made for direct observational study that was done by the surveyors in the study area. Based on the observation, a scoring was done on a 5-point Likert scale and anomaly were identified and recorded on the map.

Table 5. Visual Survey Observation Template based on CPTED

S. No	Main Criteria	Variables	Standards/ Measures	Action	Observation (present/ absent)
1	SURVEILLANCE	CCTV	Locating CCTV	marking with	
2	PASSIVE SURVEILLANCE	Building Frontage	Active (openings/ entrances every 10-15 m/ eyes on street)		
			Average (openings/ entrances every 15-30 m/ some windows on street)		
			Inactive (openings/ entrances > 30 m/ no windows one street)		
3	ROAD DESIGN	Width of Road	Wide road (6m or >)		
			Narrow road (3m-6m)		
4	LIGHTING		Very good (can see other pedestrians easily at night and the lighting is adequate/ doesnot need improvement)		
			Very poor (difficult to notice pedestrians easily at night and the lighting is in adequate/ needs urgent attention)		
5	TERRITORIALITY	Maintenance	Places with poor maintenance		
		Abandoned building/ vacant plots	Abandoned buildings/ vacant plots/ isolated places		
6	ACTIVITY	Commercial or residential	Commercial		
			Residential		

Maps generated as per observational data are as follows. These maps identify the different zones having or conforming to the design parameters and areas that do not conform. Based on this observation, the surveyor has made a safety scoring for the zones.

Street Design: The street design parameter was based on the width of the road available in the study areas; accordingly, the areas with narrow road widths are identified (Figure 5).

Surveillance Map: The parameters like presence and absence of natural or passive and active surveillance was plotted for each zone (Figure 6).

Territoriality Map: The zones where abandoned structures were marked, and areas with poor maintenance were delineated in this map (Figure 7).

Legend

- Wide road (6m or >6m)
- Narrow street (3m - 6m)

Legend

- Active Surveillance
- Average Surveillance
- Poor Surveillance
- CCTV Location

Fig 5: Street Design

(Source: Author)

Fig 6: Surveillance Map

(Source: Author)

Legend

Places with poor maintenance

Abandoned buildings / plots

Fig 7: Territoriality Map

(Source: Author)

These maps were marked as per CPTED guided checklist, and the data thus recorded through observation. The next process was to records the “perception of safety” by the users.

User’s Perception Study

The scores were tabulated, and Modal values obtained for people’s perception of safety.

The following template was used as shown in Table 2. This template was based on CPTED for recording the designed interventions on the selected streets for field observation.

Table 2. Format for Recording People’s Perception

S.N	PARAMETERS	Questions based on SUB-PARAMETERS	RANK OF FACILITY IN LIKART SCALE					
			0	1	2	3	4	5
			0= absent, 1= least value, 2=less than average 3= average, 4= better than average and 5= best					
1	SURVEILLANCE	How do you rank surveillance here? (based on presence/ absence of CCTV)						
		How do you rank surveillance here? (based on presence/ absence of Guards)						
		How do you rank surveillance here? (based on presence/ absence of Police personnel)						
		How secure do you feel here (active- presence of people/ average- people sometimes/ inactive- hardly anyone around)						
		Do you feel watched by the locals around? (windows/ balconies)						
2	ROAD DESIGN	Do you feel the road is wide enough how would you rank it?						
		How would you rank the road based on the side -walk?						
		How would you rank the road based on the facilities like shade/ seating area?						
3	LIGHTING	Based on the lighting during night-time, how do you rank this place?						
		How would you rank this place based on lighting fixtures- presence/ absence?						
4	WALKING FREQUENCY	How frequently do you walk past this stretch during day? (1= least and 5= very frequent)						
		How frequently do you walk past this stretch at night? (1= least and 5= very frequent)						

5	PRESENCE OF MURALS	How do you rank the street wall drawings? (graffiti/ bad words=1 and beautiful artwork=5)
6	LANDUSE	How comfortable are you with the activity types in the locality? (shops/ commercial activities/ unsocial gatherings) How would you rank the residential nature of this area (hostile/friendly/ uninterested)

Data Analysis

Representation of survey data

The recorded data on People’s perception for each street is mapped against the data obtained through observation template. The trends on the categories (study parameters) are studied with the help of the following graphs from Figure 8 to Figure 12 as given below.

Fig. 8. Representation of tabulated data for street 1

Source: Author

Fig. 9. Representation of tabulated data for street 2

Source: Author

Fig. 10. Representation of tabulated data for street 3

Source: Author

Fig. 11. Representation of tabulated data for street 4

Source: Author

Fig. 12. Representation of tabulated data for street 5

Source: Author

Interpretation of data

The data mapping shows that the scores according to user’s perception are concurrent with the scoring as per design considerations, except for a few cases where the deviation is not too high.

The observed value of different parameters was found to be similar to a good extent on street stretches numbered 1 and 2, whereas on stretch 4 they were found to be somewhat similar.

In stretch 3 and 5, the similarity between CPTED observations and peoples' perceptions matched least, of which people perceived stretch 3 to be less safe than CPTED observation said and perceived the safety of stretch 5 to be more than the observation of CPTED.

However, it is observed that on all the five stretches there have been at least few aspects where people's perception tallied with that of CPTED.

It has been observed that on certain aspects like 'surveillance', 'road design' and 'safety as per landuse', people perception and CPTED observation have never matched. Whereas the values on lighting and Murals have tallied in most streets.

There is no parameter on which unanimity is observed across all study zones.

Conclusion

The investigation thus answered all the queries in the following manner.

- Firstly, with the help of two types of templates (refer Table 1 and Table 2), the safety scores were identified for the streets based on each parameter- for user's perception and for designer's perception.
- Secondly, they were mapped and found that there was an overlap in many of the cases. Although all parameters were found not be in concordance with each other, the study opened a scope of understanding the people's response to the design strategies
- An anomaly in the rating (in certain streets) observed could be assumed to be due to the cultural factor in the understanding the response to the 'feeling of safety'. This however opens another scope of investigation to validate or justify.

Thus, the parity observed between the CPTED forecast and the users perception on the feeling of safety indicates that CPTED is an important tool towards creating safer environment. However, integration of some more parameters presently not included in this research (which may be investigated as a future scope) may be required to instill the "feeling of safety" in the users in this study.

This calls for further investigation as to which other parameters or aspects needs to be included, and considerations to be taken in order that the people can really perceive a place as a safe place.

Since all safety audit toolkit presently used are designed using CPTED guidelines as their major frame-work, requirement of a standardized tool-kit suitable for Indian communities was found to be imperative and can be the scope of future research.

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